

**Female Entrepreneurship in Ghana: Factors of Entrepreneurial Success towards Women
Entrepreneurs**

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DECLARATION

This work has not previously been accepted for any degree and is not being concurrently submitted in candidature for any other degree.

This thesis is the result of my own investigations, except where otherwise stated. Other sources are acknowledged by explicit references.

Signed..

Personal details withheld.

Date.....24/05.2022.....

DEDICATION

This work is dedicated to my beautiful Elizabeth and my kids Reynolds, Joel and Francesca

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I would like to thank Almighty God for the strength to finish this journey well.

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ABSTRACT

Researchers have devoted considerable times and effort to ascertain the drivers of entrepreneurial success. Entrepreneurship scholars believe that entrepreneurial success is dependent on a plethora of factors including prevailing economic conditions, business climate among others. Entrepreneurship has been largely studied as generic term to reflect both men and women entrepreneurs with much emphasis on the men. This study, with particular emphasis on women in Ghana, focused on women entrepreneurs by exploring the factors that make them successful entrepreneurs.

This research employed a quantitative approach. Hypothesis were developed and tested to draw conclusion for the study. In testing the hypothesis, the researcher obtained data by administering questionnaire to the respondents of the study. One hundred and fifty women entrepreneurs were sampled for the study. The respondents were conveniently selected from the Greater Accra and the Ashanti Regions of Ghana which are the economically dominant regions in Ghana. Literature was reviewed using data from journal articles, scholarly books, and documents. The questionnaire was administered through Google Forms. The researcher employed Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) as a tool for the analysis of the primary data.

The analysis revealed that personality traits significantly impact the success of Ghanaian women entrepreneurs. The findings further showed that the competency of women entrepreneurs significantly impacts their success. The study established that the availability of resources, including funding, to women entrepreneurs significantly influence the success of their entrepreneurial ventures. The study recommended that Governmental and non-governmental organisations in Ghana should engage women entrepreneurs in seminars, workshops, and

conferences to improve their competencies and performance. Women entrepreneurs in Ghana should be supported with resources such as finance and equipment to grow their businesses. The Government of Ghana should create enabling environment for women entrepreneurs to operate through tax waivers, tax holidays, provision of land, fast-tracking businesses registration, and improving exchange rates.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

DEDICATION.....	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	iv
ABSTRACT.....	v
TABLE OF CONTENTS	vii
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	x
CHAPTER ONE	1
INTRODUCTION.....	1
1.0 Introduction.....	1
1.1 Background of the Study.....	1
1.3 Research Aims and Objectives.....	6
1.4 Research questions.....	6
1.5 Research Hypothesis.....	6
1.6 Significance of the Study	7
Source: Author 2023.....	11
CHAPTER TWO	11
LITERATURE REVIEW	11
2.0 Introduction.....	11
2.1 Introduction to the study area: Ghana	34
2.2 Women in Ghana	17
2.3 Concept of Entrepreneurship	19
_Toc1534902142.3.1 Types of Entrepreneurship.....	20
2.4 Definition of Female Entrepreneurship	22
2.5 Concept of Female Entrepreneurship	22
2.5 Defining Entrepreneurial success	25
2.5.1 Measure of Entrepreneurial Success.....	26
2.6 Motivations for female entrepreneurs.....	28
2.6.1 Economic Motivators.....	29
2.6.2 Social Motivators	30
2.8 Theories of Entrepreneurship.....	12

2.8.1 Innovation Theory of Schumpeter	12
2.8.2 Psychological Entrepreneurship Theories	14
2.10 Conceptual Framework	36
2.10.1 Internal Factors (Personal characteristics)	37
Figure 2.2: Conceptual Framework	43
Competency	43
Personality Traits	43
Entrepreneurial Success.....	43
Demographics	43
Resource	43
Opportunity.....	43
Source: modified from Namrata and Anita (2018) and Tambunan (2016)	43
2.9 Entrepreneurial Success Factors	44
2.9.1 Internal Success Factors (Personal Characteristics)	44
2.9.2 External success factors	47
2.9.3 Support Mechanisms	51
CHAPTER THREE	53
RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	53
3.0 Introduction	53
3.1 Philosophical Foundation of the Research	53
3.1.1 Ontology	54
3.1.2 Epistemology	55
3.1.3 Axiology	56
3.2.1 Positivist Paradigm (Positivism)	56
3.2.2 Interpretivist Paradigm (Interpretivism)	57
3.2.3 Critical Paradigm or Theory	58
3.4 Research Design	59
3.5 Research Methods	61
3.5.1 Quantitative Approach	61
3.5.2 Qualitative Approach	62
3.7 Population	63
3.8 Data Collection Instruments	66
3.11 Validity	69

CHAPTER FOUR.....	71
ANALYSIS OF RESULTS.....	71
4.0 Introduction.....	71
4.1 Analysis of response.....	72
4.2 Validity and Reliability.....	73
4.3 Background Information.....	75
4.3.1 Cross-tabulation of Background Information.....	82
4.4 Descriptive Statistics.....	87
4.5 Correlation Analysis.....	88
4.6 Regression Analysis.....	91
4.6.1 Functional Equation.....	92
4.6.2 Hypothesis Testing.....	93
4.6.3 Multiple Regression.....	94
4.8 Summary.....	96
CHAPTER FIVE.....	97
DISCUSSION AND INTERPRETATION OF FINDINGS.....	97
5.0 Introduction.....	97
5.1 Impact of personality traits on the success of women entrepreneurs in Ghana.....	97
5.2 Impact of competency on the success of women entrepreneurs in Ghana.....	98
5.3 Impact of demographic characteristics on the success of women entrepreneurs in Ghana.....	99
5.4 Impact of external opportunities on the success of women entrepreneurs in Ghana.....	100
5.5 Impact of resource availability on the success of women entrepreneurs in Ghana.....	101
5.6 Summary.....	102
CHAPTER SIX.....	103
CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS.....	103
6.0 Introduction.....	103
6.1 Purpose of this Research.....	103
6.2 Summary of Findings.....	103
Competency.....	108
Personality Traits.....	108
Entrepreneurial Success.....	108
Resource Availability.....	108
6.3 Recommendations.....	108

6.4 Research Contributions	109
6.4.1 Contributions	109
6.5 Recommendations for Further Research	110
6.6 Limitations of Study	111
6.7 Conclusions	112
Appendix 2	144

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

GEM	Global Entrepreneurship Monitor
TEA	Total Entrepreneurial Activity
GSS	Ghana Statistical Service
SME	Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises
UAE	United Arab Emirates
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
AMP	Austrian Market Process
LOC	Locus of Control
NBSSI	National Board for Small Scale Industries
MSMSE	Micro, Small and Medium Scale Enterprises
AGI	Association for Ghana Industries
UK	United Kingdom
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Sciences
MIWE	Mastercard Index for Women Entrepreneurs
ROE	Return on employees
ROS	Return on sales
ROA	Return on asset

LIST OF TABLES AND FIGURES

Figure 1.0 Research flow.....	10
Figure 2:1 Map of Ghana.....	11
Figure 2:2 Conceptual framework.....	44
Table 3.0 Dependent and independent variables.....	67
Table 3:1 Research Approach.....	61
Figure 4.1: Questionnaire response.....	73
Table 4. 1: Validity and Reliability Test.....	74
Table 4. 2: Age of Respondents.....	75
Figure 4. 2: Age of Respondents.....	76
Table 4. 3: Highest Level of Education.....	76
Figure 4. 3: Highest Level of Education.....	77
Table 4. 4: Number of Years in Business.....	77
Figure 4. 4: Number of Years in Business.....	78
Figure 4. 5: Number of Years in Business.....	79
Table 4. 6: Number of Employees.....	79
Figure 4. 6: Number of Employees.....	80
Table 4. 7: Annual income of respondents.....	80
Figure 4. 7: Annual income of respondent.....	81
Table 4. 8: Percentage distribution by Age and Education.....	82
Table 4. 9: Work Status and Average Annual Income.....	83
Table 4. 10: Age and Number of years in business.....	84
Table 4.11: Number of Employees and Average Annual Income.....	85

Table 4. 12: Descriptive statistics of variables	87
Table 4. 13: Correlation Matrix for study variables	89
Table 4. 14: Test for Hypothesis.....	93
Table 4. 15: Multiple Regression.....	94
Figure 6.1: Updated Conceptual framework.....	108

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0 Introduction

The number of entrepreneurs and activities pertaining to entrepreneurship has steadily grown over the years. According to various reports from the global entrepreneurship monitor and Mastercard index for women entrepreneurs, activities pertaining to entrepreneurship have been on the rise in recent times, with the number of new entrepreneurs sprouting on a global scale. Technological advancements and new infrastructural developments in the various geographical locations across the globe are creating a number of opportunities for entrepreneurs to grow and expand their businesses. As a result, researchers have taken a keen interest in understanding the topical issues regarding entrepreneurship. This has resulted in increased research activities in the area. In the current research, the focus of the study is placed on the contributing factors that make women entrepreneurs in Ghana successful. Included in the first chapter are the background information of the research, the problem statement, the objectives of the research, the research questions, the hypothesis of the research and the importance of the research.

1.1 Background of the Study

Research has demonstrated that the number of countries that have turned their attention to entrepreneurship as a source of inspiration for economic development is on the rise (Maden, 2015). It has been recognised that undoubtedly the contribution of entrepreneurs towards economic growth and job creation around the world is greatly significant (Denanyoh et al. 2013). When there are not enough traditional wage- and salary-paying occupations available, people may turn to entrepreneurship as a means of making ends meet. For example, Quagraine et al (2021) give the view that entrepreneurship might be a source of income if an economy does not have sufficient jobs or alternative means of providing wages or salaries. Women entrepreneurship as part of general entrepreneurship is gaining lots of currency lately. In recent years, it has been reported by Quagraine et al. (2021) that companies that

have been established by women across the globe are becoming many. According to the findings of the study this trend is driven by women seeking greater autonomy. Throughout the past decade, the level of economic activities undertaken by women around the world, as indicated by Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (2015), has been on the rise steadily.

There are around 25 percent to 33 percent of all private enterprises in the world owned by women, (GEM Report, 2014). For example, a study released by Statistics Canada shows that between the early 1990s and 2012, women started 33 percent of the enterprises in Canada (Statistics Canada, 2012). In 2016, an estimated 163 million women launched or ran new businesses in 74 economies throughout the world, making substantial progress for women in the entrepreneurial sphere (Mastercard index of women entrepreneurs, 2018). According to a study by GEM, females businesses generate about 20 trillion US dollars worth of consumer spending each year, and it has been predicted, this amount will reach 28 trillion dollars in consumer expenditures (GEM, 2015).

The difference between male entrepreneurs and female entrepreneurs regarding their number is reducing. Between 2014 and 2016, women's Total Entrepreneurial Activity (TEA) rates climbed by 10%, narrowing the gender gap by 5% (GEM 2018). According to the GEM (2018), the perception of women concerning availability of opportunities, established women's business ownership, women's entrepreneurial ambitions, and innovative skills of women entrepreneurs in their businesses all helped to reduce the gap. When it comes to Ghana the women entrepreneurs are making a lot of gains when it comes to setting up new businesses. For example when it comes to the percentage of female-owned businesses, Ghana placed third in the world in the MIWE (2021) report. Again Ghana also came first in 2018 in the MIWE 2018 report. This proves the fact that women entrepreneurship is on the ascendency in the country.

Regardless of the gender of a person, all human beings possess an inborn sense of entrepreneurship that is inherent to them. As argued by Cabrera and Mauricio (2017), without women's

participation in entrepreneurial activities, economic growth of countries would be skewed and there would be skewed growth patterns as well. As Jamali (2009) points out that, there has been an increasing body of study that shows that entrepreneurial activities of females, in addition to contributing to the growth of economic systems, enhances their diversity as entrepreneurs in economic systems.

Women entrepreneurs are women who create, establish, and manage one or more businesses on their own (Chatterjee, Das, and Srivastava, 2019). Entrepreneurship by women plays a crucial role regarding poverty alleviation, creating of jobs and improving the quality of life (Chatterjee et al., 2019). Concerning the creation of jobs, innovation, poverty reduction and lowering the rate of unemployment, Dzisi (2008) argues that Ghanaian women's entrepreneurial endeavours have contributed substantially through their economic activities towards the success of the economy of Ghana. Accordingly, the government and policymakers are encouraging the development of women's entrepreneurial enterprises as a catalyst for the stimulation of the growth of the economy and national development (Chatterjee et al., 2019).

There are different factors that determine an entrepreneur's success. Davidsson (2018) contends that the success of an entrepreneur is measured in terms of financial performance and profitability. Adom (2015) considers the ability to determine the success of an entrepreneur as a complicated phenomenon, because entrepreneurial success is dependent on both financial and non-financial variables. Different studies, including Fisher et al (2014) and Gorgievski et al. (2011), have also considered both financial and non-financial measures in accounting for the entrepreneurial success. In these studies, variables including community impact, personal financial rewards, personal fulfilment and satisfaction have been included in measuring the success of an entrepreneur. Successful entrepreneurs emphasized the importance of "achievement, self-reliance, competitiveness, self-initiative, self-confidence, versatility, perseverance, resilience, innovation, and maintaining a healthy body" (Fisher et al 2014). To succeed in business, entrepreneurs must be able to come up with innovative ideas, identify

and capture new opportunities, as well as taking fair risks in order to ensure that their businesses succeed (Adom, 2015).

Khan (2021) reaffirmed the need for considering, “both internally and externally, many different determinants for the entrepreneurial success of female business owners. It has been shown that self-confident individuals who are prepared to take risks, have previous work experience, and come up with new ideas are the most successful female entrepreneurs. The success of women-owned businesses is influenced by government policies, access to financing, culture, and legislation” (Muhammad, et al, 2017). Among the factors that Syed et al. (2011) discovered play crucial role in the success of entrepreneurial ventures of females were familial support, social links, and internal motivation. Another study by Rani and Hashim (2017) found that women's lack of business acumen significantly impacts their entrepreneurial success. This research will therefore examine the success factors of women entrepreneurs in Ghana.

Entrepreneurship has long been recognized as a catalyst for economic growth and development in Ghana. However, despite the significant strides made in promoting entrepreneurship, there remains a noticeable gender disparity in the entrepreneurial landscape, particularly in the representation and success of women entrepreneurs. A world Bank report in 2017 indicate that existing data regarding female entrepreneurship across the world is usually not disaggregated to reflect the real impact of women entrepreneurship (Meunier et al, 2017). This is true in the case of Ghana, as a careful look at the existing data on entrepreneurship in the country are usually in the generic terms comprising both male and female entrepreneurs. This disparity raises concerns about the untapped potential of Ghanaian women entrepreneurs and the need to identify the key success factors that can enable them to thrive and contribute to the nation's economic prosperity (Ullah et al., 2010; Yusof and Jain, 2010). Although some investigations conducted by entrepreneurship scholars revealed a link between entrepreneurial personal traits and success (Ajayi et al., 2021) reported that there is no general agreement on how to assess these abilities. Even though entrepreneurial competencies are used as a turning point for entrepreneurial

success and business (Al Mamun et al., 2019) emphasized that their fundamental concept, measurement, and correlation with entrepreneurial competencies and enterprise success should be investigated. As a result, understanding the success factors that drive entrepreneurial success is crucial, particularly for women with limited qualifications, skills, and access to resources and training (Al Mamun et al., 2019). Existing research has highlighted various obstacles encountered by women in business, including limited access to financing, societal biases and stereotypes, inadequate networking opportunities, and a lack of mentorship and support systems (Chatterjee, et al, 2019; Ozsungur, 2019). For example Coleman and Rob (2009) contend that women tend to make less money as compared to men, these challenges, coupled with cultural and institutional barriers, hinder the growth and sustainability of women-owned enterprises in Ghana.

Moreover, while numerous studies have examined the success factors for entrepreneurs in general, there is a relative scarcity of research specifically focusing on the unique challenges and success factors for Ghanaian women entrepreneurs (Makhbul and Hasun, 2011; Pun, 2011; Rususup et al., 2012; Jayan, 2013; Adom 2015, Buame et al 2013). It is crucial to bridge this gap in knowledge and understanding to create an enabling environment that promotes gender equality and empowers women to participate fully in entrepreneurial activities. Therefore, this study aims to explore and identify the critical success factors that can enhance the entrepreneurial journey of Ghanaian women entrepreneurs by employing data obtained from Ghanaian women who have established their own entrepreneurial ventures. By addressing this research gap, policymakers, business support organizations, and stakeholders can gain valuable insights into the specific interventions and strategies needed to foster an inclusive and supportive ecosystem for women entrepreneurs in Ghana. Furthermore, this research will provide women entrepreneurs with the necessary guidance and tools to overcome barriers and unlock their entrepreneurial potential, leading to increased economic empowerment and sustainable growth for both individuals and the nation as a whole.

1.3 Research Aims and Objectives

The aim of this research is to critically explore the contributing factors that enhance Ghanaian women's entrepreneurial success in Ghana. Thus providing insights into the factors responsible for women's entrepreneurial success in Ghana. To accomplish this, the study pursues the following specific objective;

1. To critically examine the personal characteristics of Ghanaian women entrepreneurs toward their success
2. To critically examine factors towards women's entrepreneurial success.
3. To provide recommendations for women entrepreneurs to enhance the performance of their business

1.4 Research questions

The above research aims and objectives of the study will be achieved by asking the following questions.

1. What are the personal characteristics that contribute to the entrepreneurial success of women in Ghana?
2. What are the factors that contribute to the entrepreneurial success of women in Ghana?
3. What measures can be employed to support the sustainability of female entrepreneurship in Ghana?

1.5 Research Hypothesis

The hypothesis of the study derived from the literature are:

H₀1: Personality traits of women “do not have a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

H₁: Personality traits of women “have a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

H₀₂: Competency of women entrepreneurs does not “have a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

H₂: Competency of women entrepreneurs “has a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

H₀₃: Demographic characteristics do not “have a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

H₃: Demographic characteristics “have a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

H₀₄: External Opportunities do “not have a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

H₄: External Opportunities “have a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

H₀₅: Resource availability does not have “a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

H₅: Resource availability has “a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

1.6 Significance of the Study

The research gap about women participation in entrepreneurial ventures, particularly in Ghana is filled through the finding of this research. The study also serves as a guide that shapes strategies to be adopted by women who are interested in engaging in entrepreneurial activities. The study also provides insights that will make policy makers create conducive environment that aids women's entrepreneurship to thrive. When attempting to construct an accurate portrait of female entrepreneurs, past studies have largely relied on qualitative methods. This study employed a quantitative approach to obtain an in-depth understanding of Ghanaian female entrepreneurs and the variables that contribute to their success.

1.7 Methodology

The research employed the quantity approach. Original reports, journal abstracts, scholarly books, documents served as sources of the secondary data for the research. Questionnaire was the main instrument employed in obtaining the primary data for the study. The fieldwork was completed in three weeks period. A typical response time to the questionnaire was 20 to 30 minutes. The questionnaire was administered through Google Forms. The email and WhatsApp accounts of the entrepreneurs were used for administering the questionnaires.

The researcher generated a link for the questionnaire, which was then sent the research respondents for them to fill. The researcher called the study participants and reminded them to promptly provide their responses. The follow-up calls from the researcher to the participants facilitated the provision of quick responses. The data obtained “were analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The data were categorised according to the many facets of the factors influencing the success of women entrepreneurs. In analysing the background information of the respondents, frequencies, percentages and cross-tabulation were computed and represented in Tables. The research hypothesis was tested by using correlation and regression analysis. Descriptive statistics such as mean rankings and standard deviation were” initially performed.

1.8 Theoretical Underpinning

Purpose of this study is to explore the factors that influence entrepreneurial success of Ghanaian women. To better understand Ghanaian female entrepreneurs success factors and explore how these factors affect entrepreneurial success of Ghanaian women, three psychological theories (trait theory, need for achievement theory, and the notion of locus of control) and one economic theory (Innovation theory of Schumpeter) will be employed in this research. The theories will be used as a guide in creating a conceptual framework for the research which will ultimately help in developing the framework for the studies, the hypothesis as well the data collection instrument.

1.8 The Structure of the Thesis

There are six chapters for this thesis. In the first chapter, the background of the research, problem statement, aims and objectives, research questions and research hypothesis as well as the significance of the study are contained. The structure of the whole thesis is also presented in the first chapter.

In chapter two, the researcher provided a discussion on the phenomenon being investigated in the current study, based on what other researchers have reported. In doing this, satisfactorily, the chapter opens with the introduction to the study area (Ghana). Subsequently, the researcher provided in this chapter a review of articles and research works regarding the objectives of the current study. More specifically, the researcher presented reviews pertaining to areas including “entrepreneurial success, measures of entrepreneurial success, the importance of women entrepreneurship, Ghanaian women entrepreneurs, entrepreneurship theories, and entrepreneurial success factors for women entrepreneurs.”

In chapter three, the researcher provided a description of the methodology employed in the data collection process. Additionally, the chapter contains an explanation on adopted philosophical position of the research, the research strategy and the approach of the study. The researcher also provided discussion on how the research validity is achieved, issues pertaining to ethical approval, data sources and data analysis. Chapter four of the thesis contains the analysis of the obtained data and the findings that are brought forth from the data analysis.

The discussions of the main findings of the study are presented in chapter five. The discussions of the findings contained in this chapter have been made in the context of the research objectives and the reports of the various researchers concerning the phenomenon being explored. Chapter six is the final chapter of the thesis. In this chapter, the contributions the study findings make to the literature are presented. Additionally, the chapter contains recommendations for future studies, limitations of the research and the conclusion of the study.

Figure 1.0 Research flow

Source: Author 2023

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

The discussion in this chapter is centred on literature regarding the dependent and the independent variables of the success of women entrepreneurs. It is a review of related studies and their findings. The chapter commences with a description of the research area (Ghana) and the object of the study (female entrepreneurs). The review is then narrowed by the researcher to cover entrepreneurial

success, factors of female entrepreneurial success, motivation for entrepreneurship, and barriers to female entrepreneurship. The chapter also discusses the theoretical foundation for the research and the conceptual framework.

2.1 Theories of Entrepreneurship

This research project is about female entrepreneurs in Ghana. The study's primary objective is to learn what makes female entrepreneurs in Ghana successful. The connectivity between entrepreneurship and other fields such as economics, management, psychology, anthropology, and others has been well documented (Dzisi and Obeng., 2013). A variety of disciplines, including economics, psychology, sociology, anthropology, management, and others, have contributed to the development of ideas that attempt to explain entrepreneurship (Simpheh, 2011). Dzisi (2008) asserts that there is no universal theory currently for entrepreneurship, instead, researchers use different theories including economic, psychology, management, sociology, and others to explain the concept of entrepreneurship.

To better understand Ghanaian female entrepreneurs and explore how these ideas hold up in a developing economy, three psychological theories (trait theory, need for achievement theory, and the notion of locus of control) and one economic theory (Innovation theory of Schumpeter) will be employed in this research. The theories will be used as a guide to creating a conceptual framework for the research.

2.1.1 Innovation Theory of Schumpeter

Schumpeter (1934) contended that entrepreneurial activity was a crucial variable in determining the success of every market-based economy. According to Schumpeter (1945), the entrepreneur is defined as the innovator, the person who introduces new combinations of factors of production. Thus the one who sees the opportunity to introduce new product, new technique for production and dynamic ways for managing an organisation for success.

Innovation was the main theme of entrepreneurship for Schumpeter (1934). Schumpeter (1934) explained that an entrepreneur does not work within the constraints of traditional technical know-how by

making minor progressive improvements to established manufacturing processes. Rather, they create new technology or products that disrupt the current status quo, disrupt organizational routines, and propel economic growth which he referred to as the creative destruction (Parker, 2018). “The entrepreneur as an innovator, according to Schumpeter, is responsible for “doing new things or doing things that are currently being done in new ways” (Schumpeter 1947), thus the creation of a new product, a new technique of manufacturing, the opening of a new market, the capture of a new source of supply, or the organization of industry are all examples of doing new things in a new way (innovation).

Entrepreneurship, according to Schumpeter, is the primary route of company cycles and economic development (Parker, 2018). Schumpeter (1934) predicted that the economy would be hit by a surge of entrepreneurial innovation, displacing old processes and goods (creative destruction). Finally, the order will be restored, and entrepreneurship will come to a temporary halt before the next wave of creative destruction occurs.” He also emphasized that unless the entrepreneur continues to innovate, both entrepreneurial activity and the gains that result are just transitory. Parker (2018) identifies three sources of innovation; knowledge spill overs, spinoffs, and universities.

In their definition, Agarwal et al. (2010) construed of knowledge spill over as involving the peripheral benefits of knowledge that accrues “to parties other than the inventor within or across organizations and networks. Entrepreneurs can learn about new technology, products, concepts, and business models through research undertaken by incumbent research and development initiatives as well as university scientific departments, according to the knowledge spill over theory (Parker, 2018).

Entrepreneurs can gain from knowledge spill overs, according to Agarwal et al. (2010), but they often do not recompense the people who create them. Knowledge spill overs are used, resulting in higher aggregate levels of innovation than would otherwise occur; this is referred to as creative construction by scholars (Parker, 2018). Despite all of the benefits of knowledge spill overs, Parker (2018) believes that they might be harmful to the incumbent. He looked at a predator-prey model and discovered that Schumpeterian creative destruction is one possible manifestation of the negative effect. Parker (2018)

goes on to say that another potential hazard of knowledge spill over is that the threat of appropriation of knowledge by entrepreneurs discourages incumbent firms from investing in innovation at all to the mutual detriment of incumbent firms and spill over beneficiaries.” As a result, both entrepreneurs (predators) and incumbent knowledge-creators may face mutual destruction.

Spinoffs are the second source of technical information for entrepreneurs (Parker, 2018). Employees who leave their parent company to pursue fresh product ideas for themselves are known as spinoffs (Parker, 2018). For example, if a research and development person makes “a discovery and the parent business is unwilling to exploit it, Klepper and Thompson (2010) argue that the individual can resign his employment and exploit the finding with his own setup. According to Franco and Filson (2006), spin-offs are prevalent in the early stages of businesses and can occur in a variety of industries, including autos, construction, and advertising. They conclude that at least 20% of newcomers in innovative industries are intra-industry spinoffs. Universities are the final source of entrepreneurial knowledge and skills (Parker, 2018). According to Scott (2008), academia has produced more than half of all new biotechnology start-ups and 57% of search engine” companies.

This theory is closely linked with this research by providing some insights into creative natures of Ghanaian women entrepreneurs and how their innovations affect their entrepreneurial success. This theory was used in developing the theoretical framework which consequently helped in the design of the questionnaires to elicit information from Ghanaian women entrepreneurs. It captures external opportunity discovery by entrepreneurs, assessment of opportunities as well as the decision to exploit opportunities. In this research, the ability of women to tap external opportunities through innovation is explored.

2.1.2 Psychological Entrepreneurship Theories

The unit of analysis in the psychological theories is the individual (Landstrom, 1998). These ideas emphasise the personal traits that characterise successful entrepreneurship. Begley and Boyd (1988) posit that traits such as risk-taking, “the need for achievement, locus of control, and tolerance of

ambiguity have gained ground in the entrepreneurship literature. In this research, the first three (risk-taking, the need for achievement, locus of control) are deemed the most relevant traits to examine the context of Ghanaian women entrepreneurs”. These theories helped in the development of conceptual framework for the studies.

a. Risk-taking propensity

The propensity of a person to take risk is thought of as their general disposition the person has towards taking chances (Antoncic et al., 2012). One of the more stable aspects of the character of a person is the person’s predisposition to take or avoid risks. According to Simpeh (2011), entrepreneurs are characterised by a greater focus on seizing opportunities, a propensity toward innovation, and superior leadership and business acumen. Therefore, they are seen to be hopeful, emotionally robust, and mentally vivacious. They are perceived as hard workers who flourish due to their competitive desire to excel and win; they are always dissatisfied with the status quo; they serve as lifelong learners who use setbacks as stepping stones. They are people who work hard and demonstrate intense commitment and perseverance towards task (Antoncic et al., 2012). They know their worth, put the needs of others before their own, and always keep the greater picture in mind.

Examining one's characteristics and behaviours and coming to the conclusion that one has the innate aptitude to be successful is necessary for any explanation or claim of entrepreneurship (Simpeh, 2011). In this research, Ghanaian women entrepreneurs attitude towards risk taking is explored. This theory was used to develop the conceptual framework employed in this research. The conceptual framework underpinned the development of the questionnaire instrument which elicit responses from Ghanaian women entrepreneurs about their risk taking behaviours.

b. Locus of Control

A person’s locus of control is an integral part of their character. In the 1950s, the idea was first presented by Julian Rotter. According to Rotter (1966), “locus of control is defined as the conviction

that one's actions will have predetermined results or will be determined by factors beyond one's control. According to Rotter (1966) there are two types of locus of control "internal locus of control," and "external locus of control. According to Rotter (1966), people who have an internal locus of control feel that they are responsible for what happens to them in life, while those who have an external locus of control attribute all occurrences in their lives to forces beyond their control like luck, chance, fate, or under the control of powerful people.

In the entrepreneurship literature, locus of control theory explains how entrepreneurs see the source of their success whether it came by personal traits or by external factors. Ho and Koh (1992) state that "people who have an internal centre of control are more likely to be successful entrepreneurs. The internal control locus has been found to be positively correlated with entrepreneurship aspirations in a student sample by Bonnett and Furnham (1991). Additionally, owners of businesses have a little greater internal locus of control than the general population, as reported by Rauch and Frese (2000). In this research, success factors of Ghanaian women entrepreneurs are explored. The researcher is exploring both internal and factors of factors which underpin the success of Ghanaian women entrepreneurs." The use of this theory is appropriate for this research as the contribution of personal factors (internal factors) and external factors to the success of Ghanaian women entrepreneurs are deeply explored to draw relevant conclusions.

c. Need for Achievement theory

Achievement need is considered the desire to excel in relation to a set target (McClelland, 1961). According to McClelland (1961), the need for achievement is imbibed into children in their early years when their parent impose high standard of excellence on them and allow them to attain this standard without interference and praise them when the children succeed. He further argues that children who are introduced to high standard of excellence often become people with high need for achievement and subsequently become entrepreneurs.

According to McClelland (1961), achievement trait comprises five key components. These crucial components of achievement trait (N-ach trait) are (a) responsibility for problem solving, (b) setting goals, (c) reaching goals through one's own effort, (d) the need for and use of feedback, and (e) a preference for moderate levels of risk-taking. McClelland (1961) pointed out that the entrepreneur was one who have high need for achievement and ready to undertake only moderate risk solutions." An entrepreneur's passion is fuelled by a desire to succeed and outperform the competition, motivation to succeed may be the only characteristic linked to the establishment of new businesses (Shaver and Scott, 1991).

The Ghanaian women entrepreneurs' motive for doing business is assessed in this research. This theory is linked with this study in that it helped in the development of data collection instruments which was used gather data on the ambitions of Ghanaian women entrepreneurs. Responses from Ghanaian women entrepreneurs was analysed to ascertain their need for achievement tendencies.

2.2 Women in Ghana

Traditional roles for African women, especially those who live in Ghana include raising children and managing resources to feed the family (Dzisi 2008). According to Amu (2004), the colonial period is where the disparity between the sexes in education in Africa has its roots. When they needed educated Africans to assist administer the colonial governments, colonialists allegedly went with the flow of their own gender bias, enrolling young boys rather than girls in school. Girls were not always taught the same courses as males, even when they were sent to school. Instead, they were given electives like "domestic science" and "the Bible in the vernacular" (Dzisi, 2008). Because marriage and childbearing were traditionally seen as women's primary roles, and all Ghanaian societies had strong pro-nationalist impulses, it is a common belief that educating boys is more cost-effective than educating girls in Ghana (Amu, 2004). Women were expected to marry as soon as they reach puberty, and formal education was not required for them to fulfil this role (Dzisi, 2008).

Women actively work in agriculture in Ghana, whether as independent entrepreneurs or in joint ventures with their spouses. They cultivate crops and rear cattle (Mumuni et al, 2013). Some of them also engage in handicrafts like weaving and ceramics, however, their access to materials varies. In Ghanaian society, women also fill several additional jobs that vary from region to region. They participate in politics, religion, and other traditional activities, for instance. In Ghana's civilizations, women typically play subordinate positions and are not accorded the same rights as men (Mumuni et al, 2013).

Research has shown that, generally, women's access to education has improved (Amu, 2004). The improvement in the access to education for women has resulted in a rise in the number of women who work in the formal sector of the economy. This also resulted in a higher concentration of women in urban areas. Amu (2004) argues that the improved access to education for women is responsible for the observable increase in the number of women who have established their own businesses. Women's perceptions have been widened by education. In the case of those with just rudimentary schooling, the desire to better one's own and one's family's lot in life is as important as marriage and having children (Dzisi, 2008). It is not only women who are adopting leadership roles in their local communities, but also in most organizations that are dedicated to improving the lives of women and children. Most Ghanaian women are employed in the private sector. Private sector employment is estimated to account for between 60 and 65 percent of Ghana's labour, according to estimates from the Ghana Statistical Service (GSS 2021). Small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs) have a disproportionately high percentage of women owners and operators (Adom, 2015). About 85% of Ghana's female labour force is employed in the private sector, compared to 75% of the male workforce (Ghana Statistical Service, 2021). Most Ghanaians in the public sector are found in teaching, nursing, and midwifery (Dzisi, 2008).

Most women in Ghana have resorted to entrepreneurship as a means to gain a living in the country (Adom, 2015). The Mastercard index for women entrepreneurial report 2021, indicates that three out of ten women in Ghana are engaged in entrepreneurial activities, and women in Ghana

vigorously pursue business opportunities despite the prevailing harsh business environment women in the country face.

2.3 Concept of Entrepreneurship

Reynolds (2005) considers entrepreneurship to be one's ability to discover opportunities or create novel economic venture. Entrepreneurship often leads to the creation of economic ventures. Per Cantillon (1755), an entrepreneur is a person who takes on the company's risk. An entrepreneur's most important job responsibility, according to Cantillon (1755), involves the ability to deal with unpredictability. In the area of business, Jennings (1994) considered everyone involved in it as an entrepreneur. Entrepreneur and entrepreneurship had taken on different meanings for numerous French economists and writers by the year 1800, with the variances mostly stemming from the peculiarities of the sector of the economy.

Say (1828), contends that the primary contribution of an entrepreneur to the business is the optimal employment of the various factors of production. He equated the role of an entrepreneur with that of a manager. Mill was attributed by Schumpeter (1945) with popularizing the word "entrepreneurship" among economists. Mill (1848) strongly believed that the 'carrying of risk' was the only distinguishing characteristic between a manager and an entrepreneur. In contrast to this notion, Schumpeter believed that 'innovation' rather than risk (Schumpeter, 1945), were the primary causal qualities of an entrepreneur (Schumpeter 1934).

According to Parker (2018), McClelland and Drucker are two of the most prominent current proponents of entrepreneurship as a discipline. When it comes to entrepreneurship, Drucker (1985) says that it's nothing more than an expression of an individual's ability to think outside of the box in the context of business and that "Innovation" is by far the most crucial aspect of entrepreneurship. To be a successful entrepreneur, McClelland (1961) argues, you must be innovative and creative.

Over the years, researchers have failed to devise a common definition of entrepreneurship, despite its widespread use in academia and a variety of fields (Bull and Willard, 1993). As stated by

Jennings (1994), each scholar has developed a concept based on their own work without being influenced by the work of others. Entrepreneurship is defined in many different ways, but this variability is necessary because entrepreneurial research is used to accomplish a variety of purposes.

Other experts consider entrepreneurship to be a phenomenon of business that encompasses a varied variety of economic ventures, since it is a widespread phenomenon. Definitions are constantly changing and adapting to the unique attributes of these different ventures of the economy. Pre-capitalist and early capitalist societies have a wide range of entrepreneurial endeavours available to them; those in later capitalism and socialist societies have fewer options and a narrower range of profitable activities through market exchange (Buame, 2000). However, despite the fact that literary definitions of entrepreneurship are ambiguous, it appears that every effort by a human being to attempt something novel is included (Jennings, 1994; Shapero, 1975).

According to Dzisi (2008), Vanderwerf and Brush (1989) studied twenty-five definitions for entrepreneurship and concluded that entrepreneurship is a commercial activity that incorporates some 'intersection' of the following human behaviours: creation, general management, and invention. The second definition of entrepreneurship considers the concept as involving the management of a business and the distribution of business resources. Entrepreneurship, regardless of its many definitions, is a human creative act (Vanderwerf and Brush 1989).

2.3.1 Types of Entrepreneurship

Various scholars have espoused various typologies of entrepreneurship, for example, Cole (1951) classifies entrepreneurship into three vis empirical, rational and cognitive. Cole (1951), posit that the empirical entrepreneur, do not introduce anything revolutionary to challenge the status quo but follows the rule of thumb. This kind of entrepreneurship takes minimal risk (Cole 1951). The rational entrepreneur, according to Cole (1951) is the one who has adequate information regarding the economic situations around him, and has the ability to put up changes which look more ground-breaking. A cognitive entrepreneur is a well informed business person who has the ability to draw upon

the vice and services of experts to be able to bring out changes that signal diversity in schemes of operation by entrepreneurs.

Danhoff (1949) also classified entrepreneurship into four; Innovation entrepreneurship, adoptive entrepreneurship, Fabián entrepreneurship and drone entrepreneurship. Danhoff (1949), assert that the innovative entrepreneur thrives on his ability to think outside the box. Innovation is the main characteristic of this kind entrepreneurship, they do rigorous experiment and put attractive possibilities into practice. Danhoff (1949) further posit that the entrepreneurs are able to undertake novel thinking processes in order to generate better and more crucial ideas of business organization and management within the economy. Parker (2018) asserts that Schumpeter's entrepreneur was an entrepreneur of this type who saw “the opportunity for introducing a new technology, a new product or a new market.”

Adoptive entrepreneurs, according to Danhoff (1949), are just copycats who set up their business mimicking existing entrepreneurs. Rather than advancing technology or improving methods, they simply replicate those of others. The risks and uncertainty faced by these entrepreneurs are less than those faced by innovative entrepreneurs. A constellation of research findings have established that imitation entrepreneurs are best suited to developing countries, since people in these countries are more likely “to imitate the technology, knowledge, and skills that are already available in more advanced nations” (Ogujiuba 2021).

Fabian entrepreneurship also known as “non-innovative entrepreneurship”, is a rigid group of entrepreneurs who do not possess the desire “to introduce new changes or to adopt new methods of production that most entrepreneurs” have been incorporating for years now (Danhoff 1949). Danhoff (1949) further posits that new technology is only adopted by them when there is no alternative to survive in the business venture and there is no option left for them. He further assert that they are usually second generation entrepreneurs who are part of a business family enterprise owned and run by their parents.

Entrepreneurs who refuse to pursue new opportunities or replicate the existing business model are described by Danhoff (1949) as drone entrepreneurs. Danhoff (1949) further found that these entrepreneurs have a very conservative attitude. That is despite significant changes to the environment and society, these entrepreneurs remain comfortable with their old-fashioned production technologies, not ready to change for anything new.

2.4 Definition of Female Entrepreneurship

According to Noor, Isa, and Shafiq (2021), a female entrepreneur is "a woman who utilises her abilities, resources, and experience to develop a new business endeavour by confronting obstacles and challenges till achieving financial gain through a commercial venture." In addition, they characterise female entrepreneurship as comprising decision-making authority, resource control, and easy information availability. According to Kothawale (2013), a female entrepreneur is "a unit of organisation relating to a service or business enterprise managed by one or more women entrepreneurs with a share capital of at least 51 percent as shareholders of the private company, limited company, or members of the cooperative society." This research adopts the definition of Noor et al (2021) which among other things concluded that female entrepreneurship is described as businesses started and operated by females or jointly owned by females with the motive of making profits or other business goals.

2.5 Concept of Female Entrepreneurship

A man's place has historically been in the ranks of business owners, who have been portrayed in popular culture as "captains of industry" (Schumpeter, 1934), lone pioneers, and lonely heroes" (Ahl, 2002; Bruni, et al, 2004). A "male stereotype prevails when we conceive of a successful entrepreneur (Eddleston et al., 2016), in part because entrepreneurs are typically portrayed with masculine characteristics such as ambition, aggression, risk-taking, and natural-born leadership (Gupta et al, 2009; Jennings and Brush, 2013). When viewed through the masculine perspective of entrepreneurship,

women who decide to start their own businesses are viewed as less respectable, credible, and devoted than males who make the same decision (Eddleston et al., 2016). Women-owned enterprises are typically overlooked by investors because they are written off as side projects or not taken seriously as full-time operations (Arenius and Autio, 2006). Therefore, gender bias and the perceived incongruity between women and entrepreneurship have been blamed for the poor performance of firms controlled by women (Eddleston et al., 2016; Jennings and Brush, 2013).”

It has been observed that women play significant roles in the various sectors of the economy. It worthy of note that women actively contribute towards the advancement of their local economy, including the agricultural sector and the services sector. For example, Seedhouse et al., (2016) report that “in Africa, women produce 80 percent of the food, in Asia, they produce 60 percent and in Latin America, 40 percent.” Global entrepreneurship monitor 2015 report says that about 20 trillion dollars in yearly consumer expenditure is generated by females each year, and this figure is predicted by the end of this decade to reach 28 trillion dollars (GEM, 2015). It has been established that there is consistent rise in the entrepreneurial activities of women across the world (Hattab, 2012). The Global Entrepreneurship report 2015 indicates that there has been a continuous rise in the level of economic activities undertaken by women around the world over the past decade, (GEM, 2015). The global entrepreneurship monitor 2021 report indicates that “in 2020, there were six economies in which the level of female entrepreneurship exceeds that of their male counterparts. All these economies are found in Central, East Asia or Middle East and Africa (GEM, 2021).

An increasing number of studies have revealed that women's participation in entrepreneurship not only promotes economic growth but also increases the variety of entrepreneurship across all economic systems (Eddleston and Powell, 2008). According to Hattab (2012), women are participating at high levels in Lebanon and Sudan, and even though men make up a disproportionate amount of all entrepreneurial activity, a cross-country comparison of female entrepreneurship in Middle Eastern and North African countries reveals that more women are turning to entrepreneurial roles, though their

percentage is still low compared to their male counterparts (GEM 2019). The majority of women-owned enterprises in Africa operate at the micro scale, are mostly driven by necessity, and are financed by individual savings and family members (Adom, 2015). According to the MIWE, 2021 report, “there has been a rise in female entrepreneurship motivated by necessity or opportunity in South Africa (62.8% to 91.2%) and Angola (49.5% to 89.7%). This is supported by Nziku (2013), Dvoutley and Orel (2020), and Halkias et al. (2011), who discovered that female entrepreneurship in Africa remains driven by micro-financing and family dynamics, and family plays a crucial role in shaping the female-run business.

Despite the numerous obstacles these women faced in their respective countries, the Mastercard index for women entrepreneurs reports that in 10 economies, comprising “Uganda, Ghana, Angola, Saudi Arabia, Vietnam, Philippines, Nigeria, Indonesia, Thailand and Costa Rica,” entrepreneurial activities of women in 2021 outpaced those of men. The results support the most recent updates from the global entrepreneurship monitor 2021, which demonstrate how women in these regions are overcoming obstacles to be successful in their entrepreneurial endeavours. According to the survey, this is most likely motivated by women's aspirations to become more financially independent, which are encouraged by positive and healthy entrepreneurial attitudes and beliefs. This is particularly clear in countries such as Saudi Arabia, Angola and Indonesia where a large number of women are business owners motivated by a desire to change the world and enhance their wealth/income (MIWE, 2021).

The absence of financial possibilities and the removal of barriers to obtaining accessible finances are two major factors in the limited success of female entrepreneurs (Adom, 2016; Nziku, 2012). According to the findings of the research conducted by Brush et al. (2002), women business owners do not get what is due them of venture capital funding, especially as their companies expand. The long-term growth of female entrepreneurship in Africa could be boosted by making it simpler for women to launch their enterprises (Iwu and Nxopo, 2015).

According to Pablo et al. (2018), entrepreneurs define entrepreneurial success as having personal fulfilment, positive customer relationships, a positive impact on the community, and firm growth. The weight they give to each of these factors also differs. Despite the agreement that challenges exist regarding the growth of membership in the field of women's entrepreneurship, this varies across countries. According to the Global Entrepreneurial Monitor (GEM), there is ample evidence that the number of entrepreneurs has increased, and this implies that entrepreneurship is growing (GEM 2016). The findings of Ferreira et al. (2015) established that women entrepreneurship is still one of the most significant unexploited avenue of innovation, economic growth and job creation in both developed and emerging economies. In general, women's entrepreneurship is critical to the prosperity of a nation. In light of this, productivity, competitiveness, and the potential for economic growth could all be negatively impacted by barriers to women's entrepreneurship (Adom, 2015).

2.5 Defining Entrepreneurial success

Research has shown that profitability, sales and growth are not the only variables for business success (Jodyanne, 2016). These researchers argue that another crucial variable worth considering is long-term operations. The researchers are of the view that longevity and survival are attributes of successful businesses. According to Achtenhagen et al (2010), researchers have seen entrepreneurial success as the growth of the firm. Thus growth in sales, profit, or employees as compared to other firms in their industry (Senna et al. 2021). According to Senna et al. (2021), this definition considers both monetary and non-monetary indicators of success for entrepreneurs, with the latter being documented from the perspective of the organization's performance. Indicators like sales growth, employee expansion, profit margin, “return on investment (ROI), return on assets (ROA), return on sales (ROS) and return on employees (ROE) are all ways to gauge monetary success (Maharati, 2010).

Non-financial success, on the other hand, can be gauged by looking at how the venture has changed over its first five years of operation. This can be done through metrics like survival rate, customer value creation, personal achievement, public recognition, and long-term sustainability, to name

a few (Maharati, 2010). In broad terms, a company's success may be measured by its impact on shareholders, employees, or the local, national, or global economy (Duchesneau and Gartner, 1990). Shepherd and Wiklund (2009) observed that not all entrepreneurs are growth-motivated, and they further argue that entrepreneurs utilize other variables in addition to the firm's development as a measure of success.

Successful entrepreneurs' feelings of mastery over problems are measured by Jenkins and Mckelvie (2016) as success. Success can be measured in terms of the profitability or survival of the business, or in terms of the entrepreneur's and his or her family's well-being, depending on the context (Reavley and Lituchy 2008). A family firm may have a different success objective that is only understood by family members, according to other researchers (Beaver, 2003; Reavley and Lituchy., 2008). There are many different ways that entrepreneurs in the same industry can define success, depending on their motives for beginning the business and the aims and objectives they have set for themselves and their company (Reavley and Lituchy, 2008). In this study, definition of entrepreneurial success is adopted from Reavley and Lituchy (2008) which states that success can be defined in terms of the profitability or survival of the business, or in terms of the entrepreneur's and his or her family's well-being.

2.5.1 Measure of Entrepreneurial Success

The ability of a firm to withstand challenges and take advantage of opportunities to better the lots of shareholders and employees, as well as please customers maybe be a critical measure for women's entrepreneurial success (Adom, 2015). The nature of the business may affect how people perceive success. According to Yunus (2016), the success of an entrepreneur is determined by the kind of personal satisfaction the owner of the business obtains. This is because, the business is developed around the vision of a person or few individuals who establish the business. Other scholars such as Namrata and Anita (2018) believe that growth in business reflects in sales growth, “market/customer size, profit

growth, and perceived years of survival of the business are measures of women's entrepreneurial success. This research adopts these variables as a measure of entrepreneur success."

a. Business Growth

Growth in business over years is a sign of entrepreneurial success. Being able to grow a business from the scratch in a competitive business environment, coming against all the odds, and still possessing the ability to expand a business constitute a mark of business success (Jenkins, 2017). According to Namrata and Anita (2018) maintaining consistent sales growth is a measure of entrepreneurial success because sales growth contributes to overall business growth. To achieve sales growth, Afolabi (2020) asserts that prospective orders and conversion rates serve as the two specific basic drivers that every entrepreneur needs to understand. The understanding of these elements make entrepreneurs appreciate how the leads become opportunities and prospects become customers. In the event that an organisation fails to realise sales, it will become difficult for such an organisation to succeed as it will be extremely difficult attracting customers and investors. Eventually, the business will not be able to experience steady growth (Namrata and Anita 2018). It is noteworthy that growth in sales has a positive effect on the level of profit of the business which is the ultimate aim of most entrepreneurs.

Another determining factor of the growth of a business has to do with the employment level of the business: the number of people the business hires as employees. Many businesses start with few employees but as the business expands they take on more employees (Dzisi and Obeng, 2013). Some entrepreneurs even start with family members and later on bring on others when the business begins to grow.

b. Years of Business Survival

According to Jenkins (2017), longevity in Business is a crucial attribute in measuring the success of entrepreneurship. It has been noted that businesses which are considered successful are noted for providing continuous goods and services. It is worthy of note that such successful businesses are not

surmounted by the economic challenges, still operates irrespective of changes in the business world. In this regard, Menicucci and Paolucci (2016) established that businesses that are poised for longevity put in place plans that sustain them for future. According to several studies, only 5% of new enterprises survive for five years, and 90% fail during the first three years (Adom, 2015). A business is difficult to run, and requires constant adjustment like diversifying the products. For example, if one of these industries is affected by a downturn, diversification will protect the business by dealing with a wide range of products and clients.

c. Customer Base/Market share

Running a business in a fixed marketplace involves stern competition, therefore, acquiring customers is a prerequisite to being successful as an entrepreneur. For a business to prosper, Adom (2015) recommends that “businesses employ tactics to develop their customer base, by recruiting new consumers and also giving existing customers a reason to come back, engage with the brand beyond your products, and join an exclusive brand community. Brand supporters need to be created. These are usually the loyal customers who will continue to purchase with you, suggest new customers to you, and engage with you in many ways” (Jenkins, 2017).

Scholars such as Dzisi and Obeng. (2013) and Adom (2015) consider market share as a crucial determinant of the success entrepreneurial business. It is the percentage of the whole market that a single company holds. The company with the most market share is referred to as a brand leader. If a company's market share is tracked over time and compared to its closest competitors, it can be a good indicator of how successful it is (Dzisi and Obeng, 2013). This current study research will employ the indicators mentioned above as a guide in ascertain the determining factors of entrepreneurial success among women entrepreneurs who are Ghanaians.

2.6 Motivations for female entrepreneurs

It has been hypothesized that a constellation of “push and pull” elements motivates female entrepreneurship (Anthopoulou, 2010; Nziku, 2013; Adom, 2015). These findings imply that both positive and negative external and personal situations may affect the decisions women in starting their businesses. Research has reported that the tendency for female entrepreneurs to conceive the idea of starting their own businesses is higher than their male counterparts, because of a combination of negative and positive variables, (Orhan and Scott, 2001). Kalyani and Mounika (2016) indicated that, women's motivations for starting their own businesses go beyond the traditional norms of financial gain, employment independence, personal growth, and well-being

Employer and employee relationship dissatisfaction, a hostile corporate environment, and a glass ceiling are some of the factors that drive people to become entrepreneurs (Gadar and Yunus, 2009; Ismail et al, 2012). Research has shown that there are many reasons that explain the reason why women appear more likely to start their own businesses than their male counterparts. These reasons comprise the desire for more flexibility in their work schedules, a desire for personal growth and development, a desire for financial independence, an interest in a particular field of work, as well as the skills, experience, and “drive to succeed that they bring to the table (Orhan and Scott, 2001; Ismail, Chowdhury and Shamsudin 2012). A combination of these forces is the most powerful motivator for female entrepreneurs around the world, but this is especially true in developing countries (Gadar and Yunus, 2009). Research into the motivations of female entrepreneurs has been divided into three categories: social, economic, and personal (Fielden and Davidson, 2005; Coughlin, 2002).”

2.6.1 Economic Motivators

According to the push and pull theory of entrepreneurship, one of the common motivators for women to start their businesses is the desire to provide a source of income (Adom, 2015). Coughlin (2002) noted that the rise of single-parent homes and the resulting rise in divorce rates have led to women in developing countries such as Ghana being the primary breadwinners. Dzisi (2008) and

Coughlin (2002) argue that the lack of economic prospects for males in developing nations has impacted women's perspectives on male assistance.

It has been observed that the primary motivation for female entrepreneurs in Tanzania is to make enough money to meet their family's basic needs or to raise their income so that they can contribute to the family. (Ssendi and Anderson 2009; Ndziku 2013). According to Ayadurai and Sohail (2005), the majority of Sri Lankan women who become entrepreneurs did so to improve their level of living, become financially independent, and support their families. Furthermore, in Somalia, women are typically seen as major carers for their children and their families (Ali and Ali, 2013). Due to their primary responsibilities as economic producers, Somali women, married or not, have started their enterprises and run them successfully (Ali and Ali, 2013). Female business owners in Uganda stated that their primary motive for starting a business was the desire to make money or earn a living (Benzing and Chu, 2009). Increasing income is the most important motive for female entrepreneurs in Ghana (Dzisi, 2008). Women in poor nations have been pushed to explore launching a business as an alternate source of income because of financial constraints. Women's ability to take charge of their financial destiny and demonstrate their tenacity and resiliency through the rise in the number of female entrepreneurs driven by economic incentives is well demonstrated by this trend (GEM, 2018).

2.6.2 Social Motivators

Taking care of one's family and earning a living are no longer intertwined with modern culture (Anthopoulou, 2010). A common illustration of this is the necessity of working long hours away from one's family and home to make a living. Workplace dissatisfaction, the income gap between men and women, a scarcity of child care options, poor working conditions, and the need for more flexible scheduling all fall under the category of social factors that encourage women to start their businesses (Coughlin, 2002).

Coughlin (2002), on the other hand, asserted that women prefer to combine their job and family responsibilities rather than keep them separate. Thus, by establishing businesses, female entrepreneurs create an environment in which women are in charge of when, how, and where they work, despite typically putting in greater hours than they would when employed by someone else.

A study by Vatharkar (2012) found that in India, female entrepreneurs established their firms due to the opportunity it offered them in managing their personal lives and the business ventures they operate. In the United Arab Emirates, according to Itani., Sidani and Baalbaki (2011), women choose to start their businesses because of the freedom it gives them, especially when it comes to taking care of their families. In many underdeveloped countries, such as Africa, there is no obvious distinction between home and workplace responsibilities, making it difficult to distinguish between the two. Thus, women entrepreneurs who run their own businesses are more prone to getting married and bear children, because working for themselves gives them more control over their schedules (Amu, 2004).

2.6.3 Personal Motivators

Personal motivators, according to Parvin et al. (2012), include a need for fulfilment, a desire to have control over one's future, and a desire for independence. According to Coughlin (2002), female entrepreneurs find these types of motivators to be the most compelling. There is also a strong desire for self-fulfilment even in underdeveloped countries, where the primary motivation of most female entrepreneurs is economic (Coughlin, 2002) Females need an opportunity to earn respect for their qualities and accomplishments because many civilizations in developing countries treat them with little regard (OECD, 2004). It has been shown that the most significant barrier to female entrepreneurs in Nigeria is a lack of respect in society, particularly from their male counterparts. The study also indicated that Nigerian female entrepreneurs enjoy the most success when they can determine their work schedules (Babalola, 2009).

Studies on the characteristics of female entrepreneurs have found that many women are driven by a desire to succeed (Babalola, 2009). Entrepreneurial endeavours are seen to be particularly attuned to this intense demand for accomplishment. When it comes to deciding whether or not to become an entrepreneur, women in Malaysia are influenced by a strong need to express themselves creatively as well as a desire to discover their inner talents (Hossain et al., 2018). In addition, these female entrepreneurs' desire to demonstrate their business skills and the motivation that comes from their jobs reinforces their decision. For the most part, Moroccan female entrepreneurs were drawn into business because of a good market opportunity or an opportunity to buy an existing company, sometimes passed down from family members or related to their educational fields such as dentistry or pharmacy, according to Gray and Finley-Hervey (2005). Some personal characteristics that influence female entrepreneurship in Bangladesh include the need for social status and the flexibility to work (Parvin et al., 2012).

It is clear from the findings in the literature that “female entrepreneurs in underdeveloped economies that there is no single motivating element (Dzisi, 2008). Their motives are influenced by a wide range of external and personal factors. The reasons for female entrepreneurship vary from place to country, which emphasizes that it is situational or culturally bound, despite the fact that some of the causes are universal. Motivators that are proven to be push factors for female entrepreneurs in underdeveloped nations tend to be pull factors for female entrepreneurs from wealthy countries (Dzisi, 2008). Entrepreneurship in wealthy countries like the United States and Australia is mostly motivated by a desire to be recognized by others, but in transitional and developing countries, economic motives are the key motivators. Female entrepreneurs around the world appear to share a common desire for self-fulfilment and economic empowerment that comes with taking control of their lives, being responsible for their own futures, and gaining the freedom and flexibility” to pursue their dreams (Dzisi, 2008).

2.7 Barriers to women entrepreneurship

According Dzisi (2008), the full potential of women entrepreneurs has not been realised due to the myriad of problems they face as women entrepreneurs in their business endeavours. Adom (2015) asserts that some of these problems include no access to working capital, difficulty in marketing their products, inability to access Government support as well as personal and social challenges. This is corroborated by Lyngsie and Foss (2017) who report that entrepreneurial women are confronted with certain difficulties in their quest to establish enterprises and make them grow. According to Lyngsie and Foss (2017), the challenges women face as entrepreneurs, including cultural restrictions, lack of access to information, lack of resource and networking, are gender-based. Additionally, the women entrepreneurs has the onus to combine work-family duties and tend to have low-level risk-taking capacity. Mention has also been made regarding limited access to funding, gender-based stereotyping and traditional role of women as variables within the basket of entrepreneurial challenges women face.

Limited opportunities for funding (capital) has been considered a major problem women entrepreneurs are facing (Adom, 2015). Although female entrepreneurs need to compete with their male counterparts to obtain funding from the same funding sources, the task has appeared increasingly demanding, success of women in this area is very limited (Dzisi, 2008). Access to credit from banks and official funding usually requires huge collateral which women tend not to have (Yadav and Unni, 2016). Several studies cited by Coleman (2000) indicate that banks tend to favour large and medium-sized firms over small ones, which is where most of the businesses owned by women fall. Evidence from the year 2000 suggests, for instance, that women-owned businesses may have a harder time securing conventional funding due to their unique qualities (Coleman, 2000). According to Adom (2015), this is due to women's lack of financial confidence and inexperience negotiating with banks. In addition, financial institutions demand substantial collateral from female entrepreneurs before lending to them since they see loans to women as riskier than loans to men.

One obstacle to women's business ownership is the pervasiveness of sexism in our culture. In a study conducted by Crampton and Mishra (1999), it was reported that women are expected to do more of the physical labour associated with maintaining a home than men are. This is only one of the many misconceptions that women confront. Second, women tend to take on a 'greater level' of responsibility around the home (Crampton and Mishra, 1999). The third and most disheartening is that men are given greater respect for their work than women, as stated by Crampton and Mishra (1999).

The pressure to fulfil both motherly and professional responsibilities can be a hindrance to female entrepreneurs. This is a reference to the worry that Dzisi and Obeng (2013) raises about the demands placed on women company owners by the need to be both a working businesswoman and a full-time mother. Globally, women shoulder the bulk of family responsibilities, and this is true even if they have their businesses or are in the professional workforce (Brush, 1997). This role stress may cause time fragmentation, making it harder to pursue entrepreneurial activities (success) or advance one's career as a whole, as confirmed by Brush (1997) and Namarata and Anita (2018). Still (1996) claims that women who try to juggle both roles may suffer from what he terms "time poverty," which can add extra pressure and difficulties to their lives.

2.8 Introduction to the study area: Ghana

The research area, Ghana is one of the countries located in the sub-Saharan Africa. Geographically, Ghana is located on the Gulf of Guinea. The population of the country is 30.8 million, "according to the 2021 population and housing census (Ghana Statistics Service, 2021). Ghana is divided into 16 administrative regions which include Greater Accra (the capital), Volta, Eastern, Western, Northern, Savannah, Upper east, Upper West, Central, Western north, Oti, Bono, Bono east, Ahafo, Ashanti and North east. Fig.1 illustrates a geographic breakdown of Ghana by region. There are 92,100 square miles in Ghana. There are more than 80 indigenous tribes and tribal languages in the country (Dzisi, 2008). Twi is the primary language spoken in Ghana's southern regions, while Dagbani

is the primary language spoken in the north and the English Language is the official lingua franca of the nation”. At the northern boundary of Ghana, Burkina Faso is located, and the western boundary is shared with Côte d'Ivoire. Togo is at the eastern boundary of Ghana, while the Atlantic Ocean occurs at the southern boundary.

Ghana has been practicing democracy since the inception of the 1992 Constitution, making the country one of the strongest democracies in Africa. There have been a total of eight presidential and parliamentary elections since 1992 when the nation returned to democratic rule. Ghana's economy is a hybrid of state and private sectors. The agricultural sector of the economy contributes 19.71% of the overall gross domestic product. As indicated by the Ghana Statistical Service (2021), the services sector contributes 45.93%, while the industry contributes 28.26% gross domestic product.

The most predominant religions in Ghana are Christianity, Islam and African traditional religion. According to the 2021 population and housing census the percentage of Christians in the country is 74.7%, percentage of Muslims is 20.4% and percentage of traditional religion and other religions including those without a religion is 4.9% (GSS 2021).

Figure 2.1: Map of Ghana showing regional administrative capitals

Source: Ghana Statistical Service (2021)

2.10 Conceptual Framework

Figure 2.1 below “presents the proposed conceptual model of the study for the analysis. The conceptual framework proposes the relationship between business success factors and entrepreneurial success. In the research of Namrata and Anita (2018), it is explained that one needs to study the determining factors of entrepreneurial success of women in different countries. According to the researchers, this has the potential of helping a new entrepreneur discover useful information that would help in laying solid foundation of the business and growing existing business into bigger ones. The on-going discussion surrounding entrepreneurial success factors continues to draw great interest. The conceptual framework is premised on the psychological and economic theories. Kanayo and Rensburg (2020), conceptualized entrepreneurial success as the financial and non-financial performance of a business. The concept of entrepreneurial success continues to be a widely investigated element by

various researchers to try and pinpoint an exact or possible scientific relationship between internal and external factors and which factors” truly cause consistent business success.

2.10.1 Internal Factors (Personal characteristics)

Personality traits including optimism, risk-taking, and the desire for achievement, age, gender, education, experience in the workforce, and competency are among the demographics studied as well as external factors. Robbins and Judge (2009) found that qualities like internal locus of control and tolerance for ambiguity had a significant impact on professional achievement. Habib (2013) claims that the traits most indicative of entrepreneurial success are a willingness to take chances, as well as innovation, creativity, persistence, self-confidence, a positive attitude, the ability to solve problems creatively, a need for autonomy, and a willingness to take calculated risks. Strong evidence was also established between entrepreneurial qualities and the success of businesses in Malaysia by Noor. et al. (2021).

According to Bulanova et al. (2016), businesswomen are not afraid of hard labour, but they do recognise the importance of time management. Women understand their workload may be greater than that of their peers, but they take pride in their adaptability and confidence in their capacity to succeed regardless of the obstacles they face (Bulanova et al, 2016). As King-faiHui (2006) pointed out, entrepreneurs' achievements may be attributed to their sense of self-efficacy, sense of agency, capacity for making decisions, and willingness to take risks. Desai (2001) found that emotional stability, human ties, consideration, and tactfulness are crucial success factors.

According to a study by Ehigie and Umoren (2003), women company owners' perceptions of their success as entrepreneurs are heavily influenced by their self-concept, their belief in their management ability, their level of stress at work, and their dedication to their firm. It was agreed upon by Obschonka et al. (2011) that an entrepreneur's performance is influenced by his or her characteristics, including risk tolerance, self-assurance, intelligence, and the desire for success.

Similarly, an entrepreneur's level of education is a factor in their business's ultimate success or failure. A person's ability to start a business, present new products to the market, and manage that business will all benefit from education. Specifically, Kolvereid (1992) observed that those with lesser levels of education tended to have less interest in expanding their businesses. Because higher levels of education help business owners better serve their consumers and increase their bottom line, they are a critical factor in a company's overall success. Different people put more or less weight on formal education as a means to achieve success in the world of business (Barouni and Broecke, 2014).

Educated business owners, according to a number of experts, are better able to oversee their operations. "In order to be successful in business, entrepreneurs need a wide range of abilities, including the ability to read and do basic math. Inferring a potentially sizable impact of primary education on business success. A well-educated workforce is an asset to every company, says Barouni and Broecke (2014). Barouni and Broecke (2014) argue that an entrepreneur's level of education is a critical factor in his or her chances of long-term success. According to Starsia (2010), an entrepreneur's consistency with operational goals and achievement of their vision, mission, and goals will increase as a result of their level of education. An entrepreneur's critical thinking and drive to compete with others for business advantages can benefit from education" (Holtzman and McManus, 2014). According to Barouni and Broecke (2014), to turn a profit as an entrepreneur, you need to develop the people skills necessary to persuade buyers to buy your wares. However, Amu (2004) reports that women in Ghana have lower literacy rates than men, which means that they have less access to education and training in areas like money management and the fundamentals of running a business, managing employees, navigating the market, and securing resources.

The author highlights work experience as a personal trait of entrepreneurial women that can influence their successes. Jo and Lee (1996) state that "work experience" means the knowledge an entrepreneur gains while establishing and running a previous business. That is the length of time and the function that prior entrepreneurs played in their businesses. According to Temitope and Sharma (2019), "the majority of female entrepreneurs in industrialised nations are in the second half of their career lifecycle, when they have the education and knowledge to launch their own business (Temitope and Sharma 2019). Women with less education and experience in the workforce are less likely to become entrepreneurs than those with higher education and more than five years of experience in the workforce (Temitope and Sharma 2019).

Management, teamwork, sales, cooperation, and industrialisation are just a few of the areas where Inmyxai and Takahashi (2010) claim that previous and present work experience can be converted into useful knowledge and abilities. In addition, Inmyxai and Takahashi (2010) argue that entrepreneurs who have had prior experience are more likely to be successful since it shows that they have developed as business people. Ipate and Parvu (2014) agree that an entrepreneur's ability to operate a business effectively increases as their level of experience in that field does. It has also been said that women who are more likely to engage in entrepreneurial activities have substantial work experience and technical know-how, both of which are advantageous when launching a new venture. Many researchers have confirmed that an entrepreneur's age has a significant impact on his or her company's performance. Hambrick and Manson (1984) discovered in the early 1980s that age is connected with conservative conduct and, as a result, has a detrimental impact on business success for three (3) reasons. For starters, an elder entrepreneur is less likely to try new things or embrace fresh ideas. Second, an older entrepreneur is more likely to be committed to a specific organizational status quo. Finally, goals relating to pay and job stability will encourage more cautious behaviour. As a result of previous research, it has been indicated that younger entrepreneurs are more likely to take risks and innovate in order to build their businesses (Hambrick and Manson, 1984).

Women's business performance in two districts in Ghana's Central Region was explained by Amoako-Kwakye (2012), who found that age was an important policy variable. Clark (2010), on the other hand, discovered that women's trading relationships were not affected by their age. Furthermore, the findings of this current study show that internal factors have a key role in the success of female entrepreneurs in Ghana. Thus, for the entrepreneur, research has established that the success of a business continues to vary depending on personality, competency, demographic characteristics. This notion is supported by the assertion made by Kirkwood (2016), who reiterated that entrepreneurial success could either be associated with characteristics of the business itself or the person who operates or owns the business.

2.10.2 External success factors

The conceptual model (fig. 2.1) depicts that entrepreneurial success is dependent on both internal and external variables. External factors consistently pave the way toward achieving maximum business performance. External factors include variables such as business opportunities (market share, networking relationship, and economic conditions), resources (source of funds, family support, and government support). Additionally, Parwez (2017) cited a well-designed marketing plan and strategy as a significant business success element, while Varadarajan (2018) cited the availability and access to capital and technology.

Lack of easy access to capital is still an issue for budding female business owners. According to Adom and Asare-Yeboah (2016), failure in obtaining capital/finance access is one of the main hindrances to the progress of women-owned businesses. According to Adom and Asare-Yeboah (2016) and Tambunan (2016), securing funding and capital can be one of the most difficult obstacles for an entrepreneur to face while starting a business. Bank loans, equity finance, crowdfunding, and grants are all options for start-up financing (Adom and Asare-Yeboah, 2016). There are benefits and drawbacks to every possible funding option. A bank loan gives the borrower complete discretion over the company,

while equity-based funding gives the investor just partial say. However, crowdfunding needs information to be released, “which exposes information to competitors, and grants are very specific, making them both difficult to acquire and therefore less likely to be used as a source of funding (Temitope and Sharma 2019). According to Adom and Asare-Yeboah (2016), the main reason why women in poor nations and rural regions don’t have better access to funds and loans is that they don’t know about or don’t trust the official financial sector, which might provide money for their businesses. In contrast, Chinomona and Maziriri (2015) discovered that women entrepreneurs in industrialised nations either have access to their capital” or prefer to get into partnerships for equity, in addition to borrowing from friends and family.

Human capital, defined by Lepak and Snell (1999) to comprise skills, education, experience, and information gained from previous jobs, is another external factor influencing women business owners’ success. Human capital, as argued by Lepak and Snell (1999), is a vital resource that contributes to an organization’s performance and competitive edge. Ipe (2003) argues that knowledge management is essential for any business to succeed since information is a vital strategic resource (Ipe 2003). For many business owners, the success of their enterprise ultimately rests on their ability to expand their operations in response to market demands and supply constraints, which in turn is largely dependent on the calibre of their human capital (Adom, 2015). Knowledge, according to Drucker (1993), “serves as both a production base and a production factor” for businesses. Examples include the claims of Shane and Venkatraman (2000), who state that successful entrepreneurs have a high level of human capital, giving them the ability to carry out entrepreneurial duties and see business prospects.

Similarly, women's social networks can make or break their chances of being successful as business owners. According to Nziku and Struthers (2018), the foundation of any successful social network is a complex web of human relationships. Entrepreneurship can benefit from or be hampered by the degree to which individuals, institutions, and organisations are linked together through these networks (Aldrich and Zimmer 1986; Nziku and Struthers, 2018). Access to and participation in

networks (both formal and informal), such as professional organisations, is becoming increasingly important for entrepreneurs. Women's success as business owners is also dependent on their relationships with friends, family, and co-workers (Omwenga, Mukulu, and Kanali, 2013). There is a strong correlation between women business owners in developing economies and social-cultural elements (religious, family, etc.), according to a theory put forth by Balakrishnan and Low (2016).

Scholars like Namrata and Anita (2018) argue that family support is crucial to the development of an interest in entrepreneurship and, by extension, the establishment of sales and profitability for any new businesses. Jodyanne (2016) claims that to launch and grow a business, women depend greatly on their husbands' support. Women entrepreneurs may also obtain financial assistance from their business partners, and other family members.

The current economic climate of a country has significant effects on how women company owners conduct their operations. The term "economic conditions" is used to describe the monetary and fiscal factors that affect a company's performance. Trade cycles, economic resources, income levels, income distribution, and wealth are all included. It also includes the economy's system, policies, and characteristics (Parker, 2018). Labour expenses, interest rates, government policy, taxation, and management are all crucial elements of a company's economic environment (Parker, 2018). When economic indicators are consistent and predictable, businesses usually fare well (Domingo, 2017). Businesses struggle to function well in countries with unstable economic indicators like the currency rate and interest rate because they are unable to make long-term plans.

It is, therefore, imperative for entrepreneurial women to devise strategies that would enable obtain the ability to synthesise all their internal and external factors into a flexible business plans and put measures in place to realise daily targets and profitable returns in a consistent manner.

Figure 2.2: Conceptual Framework

Source: modified from Namrata and Anita (2018) and Tambunan (2016)

2.9 Entrepreneurial Success Factors

Women's entrepreneurial success, according to Guocui and Xingyuan (2012), may be attributed to “six different factors including personalities, human capital, femininity, entrepreneurial motivation, the entrepreneurial environment, and the nature of the start-up itself. Rani and Hashim (2017), mentioned human capital, networking, financial aids, and opportunity as some of the influences of women entrepreneurial success. Social capital, human capital, and reputational capital were all found to be key contributors to the growth of women-owned enterprises by Sallah and Caesar (2020). A study in Vietnam found out that rapid technological improvements, market globalisation, recent changes to the global economy such as market and trade liberalisation initiatives, and government support, have led to increasing the level of entrepreneurial success of women entrepreneurs in the Asian country (Arsalan and Ali, 2020). Marina et al. (2019), posit that personal motivation, networking and role of government have become common determinants of success in entrepreneurial activity in both developed and developing countries. Personal traits and attributes like need for achievement, honesty and locus of control have positive correlation with entrepreneurial success” (Simpheh, 2011). This section delves deep into the various success factors of entrepreneurial women in Ghana which include internal factors, external factors and support mechanisms.

2.9.1 Internal Success Factors (Personal Characteristics)

Many different factors play roles in determining the entrepreneurial success of women in their economic activities. According to research findings, one's past experience and kind of formal training received serve as an important component of the internal factors required for a business to succeed (Dzisi and Obeng., 2013). Makhbul and Hasun (2011) found that the entrepreneurs' independence, their ability to make their own decisions and their ability to control the organisations contribute to their success. Bugawa and Aljuwaisri (2021) established Internal (personal) factors such as goals, motives, entrepreneurial orientation and human capital influence the performance of women entrepreneurs. Female entrepreneurs' success is boosted by both sets of factors. Research findings have demonstrated

that the kind of formal training women have had and their level of educational attainment impact positively on their business endeavours (Namrata and Anita 2018). Cabrera and Mauricio (2017) also found that, there are a variety of elements that influence the success of female entrepreneurs at every stage of the entrepreneurial process. These factors include personal characteristics of the entrepreneurs.

Khan et al. (2021) established that women-owned businesses benefit from a combination of internal and external factors that contribute to their success. Internal factors include a desire for accomplishments, willingness to take risks, and confidence in one's own abilities. Sambul (2019), found out that Dominance, Steadiness, Compliance, Influence and Resilience were the five personality traits of female entrepreneurs that have impact on their business. A study conducted in the UK has shown that women who have received formal education to the tertiary level tend to do well when they venture into their own business (Temitope and Sharma, 2019).

According to Tlaiss (2015), women are able to overcome obstacles in their pursuit of entrepreneurship due to a combination of external success determinants and internal success factors, such as personal attributes and motivation. Namrata and Anita (2018) also highlighted characteristics like: locus of internal control, in addition to innovative, proactive, generalised self-efficacy, moderate risk trend, and stress tolerance, for achievement in business. Ummah and Gunapalan (2012), concluded that, entrepreneurial success is strongly linked to a person's personality. Entrepreneurs with a high internal locus of control, as compared to those with a low level of this feature, will be more willing to take chances, try new things, and be proactive rather than reactive. The importance of innovative thinking, a focus on the future, a tolerance for uncertainty, flexibility, and dedication were all corroborated by Singh and Ratvi (2013). Banda (2018), found that women entrepreneurs' success was tied to their "drive and resilience." From the foregoing analysis is safe to hypothesise that;

Ho₁: Personality traits of women “do not have a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

H₁: Personality traits of women “have a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

Features such as talents of women and business knowledge, the usage of expert advisors, and his or her financial situation influence their success as noted by Chong (2012). Raheem (2013) found that, individual competencies such as business management and leadership skills are critical for women success. Schneider (2016) found that, functional task-related managerial skills, entrepreneurial characteristic adaptations of self-efficacy, risk-taking and innovation orientations, and the founder and innovator identity all have positive impact on the performance the business. Rachdi (2006) found that women business owners usually “lack technical expertise and knowledge management, leading to low productivity and market competitiveness.” Cultural norms also act as a barrier to women's empowerment in decision-making roles. Based on these discussions, the researcher proposed the following hypothesis:

H₀₂: Competency of women entrepreneurs “does not have a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

H₂: Competency of women entrepreneurs “has a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

Tlais and Kauser (2019), revealed that a population that is disproportionately youthful, is essential to the economic health of a country. The impact of an entrepreneur's age, religion, gender, background, and education, as well as their level of experience on the performance of their enterprises is enormous (Welmilla et al 2011). Ummah and Gunapalan (2012), showed that family background, personality components, institutional support, had a positive impact on business success. Others in the academic community argue that entrepreneurs' socioeconomic and demographic features are crucial to the sector's success (Adom, 2016). Sajilan et al. (2015) posits that, the impact of an entrepreneur's demographic features on their business changes depending on the situation. Multiple studies have shown that an entrepreneur's age significantly affects the success of his or her business. Amin (2021) demonstrated a link between demographic factors and the long-term success of women business owners.

Among the demographic factors affecting the success of female business owners in Dhaka, the proportion of the population with a college degree was found to be a strong one. According to research conducted in the 1980s by Hambrick and Manson (1984), there are three main reasons why getting older is bad for business. To begin, a senior business owner is less inclined to take risks and more likely to reject novel approaches. Second, an established business leader tends to be more loyal to established procedures and policies. Finally, financial and job security targets will inspire restraint. Previous studies have shown that younger entrepreneurs are more willing to take risks and innovate as they grow their enterprises (Hambrick and Manson 1984). According to Dzisi and Obeng. (2013), a number of gender-related barriers affect the success of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in underdeveloped nations. According to Dzisi (2008), women face unequal rights and obligations that restrict their freedom to move professionally and place an unfair amount of responsibility on their shoulders at home. Again, Tlais and Kauser (2019) discovered that patriarchal social norms, gender roles, and expectations, as well as societal expectations of women's domestic responsibilities and childbearing roles, all have a part in limiting women's entrepreneurial development and success. It is therefore hypothesised that;

H₀₃: Demographic characteristics do not “have a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

H₃: Demographic characteristics “have a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

2.9.2 External success factors

Success factors that are external in entrepreneurship are the things that affect the success of a business other than the personal characteristics of the individual. They include economic conditions, technology, access to capital, and socio-networking which “determine the level of business operations, profit, longevity, and growth” (Brush and Cooper, 2012). Kubickova and Prochazka (2014) viewed external environmental factors such as political, economic, and socio-cultural factors, as well as technology to influence women entrepreneurs'. Bugawa and Aljuwaisri (2021) established external

(environmental) factors such as cultural, economic, legal, administrative and time management to influence the performance of women entrepreneurs. Female entrepreneurs' success is boosted by both sets of factors

The term economic condition explains the economic variables which impact the operations of a firm. Economic conditions constitute the system of the economy, governmental policies, the nature of trade cycles in the system, income levels, economic resources, wealth and income distribution (Parker, 2018). For a business, key economic factors include labour costs, interest rates, government policy, taxes and management” (Parker, 2018). Businesses tend to do well when economic indicators are stable and predictable (Domingo, 2017). In a country where these indicators like exchange rate and interest rate are not stable, businesses are not able to plan and therefore leads to negative effects on their performance. In an economy where the standard of living is high, Domingo (2017) asserts that the citizens tend to have high purchasing power and business tend to flourish in such an environment. Parker (2018) and Adom (2015) believe that good prevailing economic condition is a major success factor for businesses.

Networking is another external factor that helps businesses to succeed. Nziku and Struthers (2018) define social networking as a system of interactions in which both parties benefit from the exchange of ideas, knowledge, and contacts. According to Kristiansen (2004) there are a variety of places where would-be business owners might acquire the funds necessary to launch, expand, and ultimately succeed with their ventures. A social network consists of the core actor and all of the other actors in the sphere of contact, both formally and informally. Connecting with other business owners, whether they work for a supplier, a bank, or a customer service company, can be invaluable to a start-up's success (Nziku and Struthers 2018). Judicial and government authorities may become involved as well.

It is commonly believed that women's business success is due to their superior networking skills (Dzisi 2008). Networking, in whatever form, can be beneficial to a company's growth and success,

according to studies (Aldrich and Zimmer 1986; Baron and Shane 2005 and Nziku and Struthers, 2018). In their 2005 research of small-scale garment and carpentry enterprises in Tanzania, Kristiansen (2004) discovered that social networks have an effect on business adaptation. Nziku (2012, 2013) corroborated this, and she also argues that women's social networks are a significant factor in their decision to launch their enterprises.

Proponents of social networking argue that entrepreneurs thrive when they have a wide network of contacts. Entrepreneurship can benefit from or be hampered by the degree to which individuals, institutions, and organisations are linked together through these networks (Aldrich and Zimmer 1986; Dzisi 2008; Nziku and Struthers, 2018). Access to and participation in networks (both formal and informal), such as professional organisations, is becoming increasingly important for entrepreneurs. Knowledge and ideas shared on social media sites like Twitter and Facebook can be useful for launching and managing a business, as can the attitude of the user toward entrepreneurship as a whole.

Women business owners in Africa have a much better chance of success if they have access to capital (Jamali, 2009; Mandipaka, 2014; Adom 2015). Keep in mind that women in Ghana face unique challenges when trying to secure funding for their businesses. It's widely believed that women have it harder than males when it comes to breaking into the business world and succeeding as entrepreneurs, “despite the fact that women face many of the same challenges as men (OECD, 2004). Studies have shown that it is difficult for women in poor nations to gain access to adequate funding to launch or grow their enterprises (Jamali, 2009; Adesua-Lincoln, 2011; Mandipaka, 2014). As a result, self-funding is the norm rather than the exception for female business owners. Since women in developing countries are more likely to use personal savings and credit cards to support enterprises, they face greater obstacles when trying to gain access to financial resources (Jamali, 2009). In Zambia, for instance, just a small fraction of female entrepreneurs had access to company funding from banking institutions, while 50% of entrepreneurs used personal resources to create a firm, 10% used layoff benefits as financial capital (Richardson, Howarth and Finnegan, 2004). Businesswomen in Ethiopia often use a group lending

distribution technique and run relatively modest operations, leading them to feel that the loan products offered by traditional financial institutions are not suited to their needs (Richardso et al, 2004). Adesua-Lincoln (2011) revealed that just 19% of Nigerian women use loans from family and friends when beginning a business, whereas the majority use their savings. Not one of the women business owners surveyed had access to conventional forms of financing like bank loans. Perhaps this is because Nigerian banks and other lenders view consumer rather than business loans as the most profitable ones to make” (Adesua-Lincoln, 2011).

Investing in cutting-edge, state-of-the-art technology provides a distinct advantage over rivals and can lead to sustained growth. Technology helps spur innovation, which in turn spurs the growth of businesses, as Parker (2018) explains. From this, we learn that technological advancements are crucial to the survival of commercial enterprises. As Parker (2018) reports, British research has found that companies that incorporate IT into their processes have a higher rate of success than their peers. To produce a product or build a structure are the primary objectives of production operations. The majority of firms are involved in the creation of goods, which necessitates the use of two production factors: time and efficiency (Ramey, 2015). Technology can be used to automate some aspects of a business's production, which can enhance output and allow the business to better serve its consumers. The researcher hypothesised that:

H₀₄: External Opportunities do not have a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs in Ghana.

H₄: External Opportunities have a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs in Ghana.

H₀₅: Resource availability does not have a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs in Ghana.

H₅: Resource availability has a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs in Ghana.

2.9.3 Support Mechanisms

In order for women entrepreneurs to succeed, they receive assistance from their husbands, parents, government, non-governmental agencies and partners (Adom, 2015; Dzisi, 2008). For example, “it has been reported by the National Board for Small Scale Industries (NBSSI) that about 190,000 women-owned micro, small and medium scale enterprises (MSMSE) benefitted from government’s grant for the year 2020 (NBSSI, 2021). Support for women entrepreneurship come in various forms and shape. Adom (2015) reports that support for business can be in the form of training, access to information and financial assistance from government and non-governmental agencies.”

According to Namrata and Anita (2018), business success is highly influenced by the assistance entrepreneurs receive from their family. It is noteworthy that the support one receives from the family is crucial in creating a conducive atmosphere for the business to be formed and nurtured. Family support is a decisive factor in the success of a business venture. If one would develop interest in entrepreneurship and establish a business venture, the support of the family is crucial. According to Jodyanne (2016), there is evidence that women entrepreneurs depend largely on the assistance of their family members to start and successfully develop an entrepreneurial venture. This support comes in various forms, from the provision of free labour to financial assistance.

2.11 Summary

The literature review covered concepts and theories on women's entrepreneurship and business success. The goal of the thematic review was to obtain an in-depth understanding of the determining factors of the success of women entrepreneurs in their business activities. Three main elements were explored to reach the research aim: “personal success factors, external success factors, and support mechanisms. Entrepreneurial success is measured by profit margin/turnover, sales growth, number of

employees, and years of survival of the business. Personal success factors discussed included personality traits, work experience, and level of education among Ghanaian women entrepreneurs.

External factors discussed include access to resources and opportunities. Access to finance resources remains a critical barrier for women entrepreneurs in Ghana. Limited access to capital, high interest rates, and collateral requirements are common challenges faced by women entrepreneurs. Studies suggest that enhancing financial literacy and improving access to microfinance institutions can positively impact women's entrepreneurial success. The role of government policies and support mechanisms cannot be overstated. Studies have highlighted the importance of gender-responsive policies that address the specific needs and challenges faced by women entrepreneurs. These policies include initiatives such as business development services, tax incentives, market access programs, and gender-focused training programs. Additionally, the establishment of dedicated institutions and organizations that provide support, guidance, and financial assistance to women entrepreneurs has been found to positively impact their success

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

In this chapter, the methodology followed in undertaking the research is discussed. The philosophical underpinnings within which the research is grounded have been discussed. The discussions in the chapter consist of the research design, data collection, and the questionnaire design activities. Again, the population and sampling procedure, ethical issues relating to the current study and finally, the data analysis techniques employed in obtaining the data for the research are also discussed in this chapter.

3.1 Philosophical Foundation of the Research

Every research conducted takes its shape from specific research assumption, a philosophical position. This philosophy of research determines what should be considered genuine research. The philosophical position of the research also informs the research technique or method that is relevant in the creation of knowledge on a certain subject (Crotty, 1998). Several terminologies are used to represent the philosophical foundation of research in the literature, such as research paradigm (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016), research philosophy (Crotty, 1998), and philosophical worldview (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). To give a research endeavour credibility, many academics contend that it needs a robust theoretical framework that engages in conversation about the nature of knowledge within the project (Monrouxe and Rees, 2009). It has been explained that the chosen research philosophy represents significant assumptions of the perspective of the researcher pertaining to the world within which knowledge is to be obtained (Saunders et al, 2016). The research paradigm explains and examines in detail the nature of knowledge included within a certain work. According to Fard (2012), the notion paradigm first appeared in work of Kuhn (1962), “The Structure of Scientific Revolution.” Research paradigm is a mode of thinking that is philosophical (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017, p.26). Saunders et al. (2016), explain the term research paradigms as involving a researcher’s assumption and ideas about how

the researcher needs to interpret the world. According to McGregor and Murnane (2010) a paradigm entails a constellation of concepts, values, assumptions and behaviours involving the manner in which one understands reality. In simple terms, it is a technique for thinking about and doing research.

The need for a researcher to employ a research paradigm effectively cannot be overstated. Research paradigms should be an important part of every research, according to Brown and Duenas (2019). Paradigms also serve in creating ground rules for the application of theory when witnessing occurrences. In addition, Abdulkareem et al. (2017) opined that the research paradigm gives a unique direction for procedures in a research design. Consequently, describing one's research paradigm is vital, as paradigms guide how problems are solved, and directly influence an author's choice of methods. Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016) posited that three major philosophical thinking exist in the area of research: (a) ontology, (b) epistemology, and (c) axiology and argued that each influences the thinking about the research process, underlying research strategy, and research methods based on the researchers' assumptions.

3.1.1 Ontology

Scotland (2012) construed research ontology as a philosophical discipline that involves the assumptions that are made in an attempt to believe the existence of things or perceive things to be real. It is the very nature or substance of the social phenomenon" one is researching. It relates to the character of our reality views. Assumptions are the foundation around which we build our beliefs about the validity and veracity of what we're trying to discover in society (Kivunja and kiyuni 2017). As a researcher, it probes your core assumptions about what it means to be human and what it means to be alive. Ontology allows the conceptualisation of the form and characteristics of reality. It enables researchers to conceptualise what they consider knowable about reality. According to Scott and Usher (2004), a fundamental component of a paradigm is ontology, because ontology is responsible for making researchers understand things and their nature.

The researcher, in this thesis, uses “an ontological position of the objective approach to analyse the entrepreneurial success factors of Ghanaian women entrepreneurs and to examine how these entrepreneurial success elements contribute to their entrepreneurial journey. The social ontology approach in this research posits that Ghanaian women entrepreneurs who build up and run enterprises have their meanings and interpretations and clear beliefs on entrepreneurial success criteria (Neuman, 2011; Yin, 2014; Gray, 2014)”. Regarding this, this research adopts the survey technique by independently collecting quantitative data on the factors that contribute to the success of women entrepreneurs in their economic activities.

3.1.2 Epistemology

The notion epistemology as used in the context of research pertains to how knowledge is obtained about a phenomenon. It is concerned with the ways by which the truth regarding reality is obtained (Nguyen et al., 2019). It involves "the nature and forms (of knowledge), how to obtain it, and how to communicate it to other humans" (Cohen et al., 2000). Epistemology is a subfield of research philosophy concerned with the study of what it means to know. As a result, this method establishes a foundation for the various forms of knowledge that are required (Gray, 2014). To put it differently, epistemology is utilized to establish how much knowledge is considered sufficient, it entails assessing the researcher's relationship with his or her subject (Collis and Hussey, 2014).

Epistemology is a term that describes “how we come to know something”, such as the truth or reality, as Cooksey and McDonald (2011) put it, what constitutes knowledge in the world. Antwi and Hamza (2015) stated that epistemology is the nature of the relationship between the “knower (researcher) and what is known”. The goal of this thesis is to look into the elements that contribute to entrepreneurial success and how these factors have influenced women entrepreneurs in Ghana. By adopting a realist position new knowledge can be created deductively and a researcher can learn about reality by carefully observing the reality using objective tools to collect data.

3.1.3 Axiology

There are different axiologies that are employed in research paradigms. Some of these axiologies include “value-neutral, value-laden and balanced, biased, and culture-sensitive axiology, and value-driven axiology.” To offer a balanced report of findings, “value-laden and balanced axiology assumes that the researcher accounts for their own bias as well as that of the participants (Nguyen, 2019, p.6). Value-neutral axiology is when the researcher's values/bias is removed from the facts of the findings, in other words, research should be conducted in a value-free manner, with the researcher remaining objective and unaffected by the facts (Saunders et al., 2019). To put it another way, it assumes that research is value-bound since it is conducted by subjective humans, necessitating the need to account for their subjectivities. Axiology based on values (for pragmatics) assumes that the researcher's values have a significant part in the research (Saunders et al., 2019).” That is, the research problem(s) and research topic have an impact on the researchers. For this research, the researcher takes a value-neutral axiological approach because the researcher used questionnaires to solicit independent information from the women entrepreneurs in Ghana as well as secondary data from the Association of Ghana Industries, NBSSI and association of women entrepreneurs

3.2 Research Paradigm

Given that research paradigms impact the design of both quantitative and qualitative research and are essentially underpinning both, it is critical to choose a paradigm before beginning a study (Brown and Duenas, 2019). There are multiple prominent paradigms in social science, each having its own epistemological and ontological standpoint. Research paradigms were categorized into three by Scotland (2012), and Shah and Al-Bargi (2013): positivism, interpretivism/constructivist, and critical paradigm.

3.2.1 Positivist Paradigm (Positivism)

Deductive logic and objectivity serve as the guiding principles of positivism. Based on the premise that society can and should be understood factually and scientifically, the positivist framework functions (Babbie and Rubin, 2008). Bryman and Bell (2011) describe positivism “as an epistemic

perspective that encourages the application of natural science methodologies to the study of social reality and beyond.” It supports the premise that scientific knowledge is generated by accumulating data theory-free and value-free from observation (Creswell, 2014). It is maintained by Knight and Turnbull (2008) that positivism sees all knowledge as based on scientific experimentation and observation.

According to a broad definition, positivism is a philosophical worldview based on what is known as "factual" knowledge. Formulation of a hypothesis has been noted to be the genesis of deductive data analysis. It is worthy of note that the formulated hypothesis is then tested statistically to determine if it is true or not. The goal is to monitor, control, anticipate, build laws, and ascribe causality to anything from weather patterns to human behaviour (Cohen et al., 2000).

This research uses an empirical research methodology in order to answer the research questions. Overall, positivist philosophy is needed for this study to achieve its goals. The justification for selecting a positivist or quantitative method is that these approaches perform better in studies intended to test hypotheses (Hussey and Hussey, 1997). It is possible to suggest that the positivist paradigm, based on the quantitative approach, is appropriate for the goals of this study because it is intended to evaluate hypotheses. The positivist paradigm's primary goal is to support or refute hypotheses, its focus is thus consistent with the objectives of the ongoing research.

3.2.2 Interpretivist Paradigm (Interpretivism)

In the interpretivism paradigm (also known as constructivism or phenomenology), the social world is made up of meaningful acts (Bunniss and Kelly, 2010). Research in the humanities can benefit greatly from this method. Researchers must be able to empathize with individuals and groups to grasp and make sense of what is going on and what they mean when they talk about their activities and interactions. It has been noted that Interpretivism gathers large qualitative data from research participants over a long period in the course of conducting ethnography and case study research (Tavakol and Sanders, 2014). The reason is that "they tend to perceive theory as coming from data

gathering and not as the driving force of research," interpretivism utilises "the inductive technique instead of the deductive approach. Inductive data analysis is used to uncover patterns in the data, which are then grouped into broad themes to comprehend a phenomenon" and build a theoretical framework (Grix, 2004, p. 108).

3.2.3 Critical Paradigm or Theory

Critical thinkers believe that social reality is made up of historical events that have been re-created by individuals (Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). According to critical scholars, social, cultural, and political dominations limit people's power to change their socioeconomic and political situations (Fard, 2012; Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017). Positivist inquiry aims to anticipate and explain, while critical theory seeks to introduce cultural, political, and social change in order to eradicate the sources of disenchantment. Critique acknowledges prejudice in every human action, and it expects the findings to back up that bias (Okesina, 2020). To maintain objectivity, the researcher must be as transparent as feasible and conduct their research in such a way that prejudice does not affect their findings. However, there have been some criticisms of critical theory. Because of the inherent subjectivity of this form of research, it is not always possible to determine with certainty the best tactics to use to meet the study's objectives (Okesina, 2020).

3.3 Chosen Research Philosophy for this study

Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016) claimed that more than one philosophical paradigm is employed in conducting research in the area of business and management. Building on the understanding of the philosophical foundations and research aims and questions, this study adopted the positivist research paradigm. This paradigm directs the choice of a data collection method in this study. As this research aims at identifying and exploring the determining factors that lead to the success of Ghanaian women entrepreneurs in Ghana by using scientific models, the positivism research philosophy is considered appropriate for this study. The philosophy enables the researcher to independently gather and analyse data for attainment of the objectives of the study. This study used a positivist research

philosophy that relies on the testing of hypotheses by using a self-administrated survey-based quantitative data collection method. Moreover, as the researcher's focus is to test the theories, the study used a deductive approach in which the hypotheses are first developed and then tested using a specific research strategy (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). Therefore, the positivist philosophy and a deductive approach underpinned this research.

3.4 Research Design

When conducting research, it is important to know exactly “how the research will be conducted to answer the research question (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). As a researcher, you are guided by a research design. How the researcher intends to carry out the research is depicted (Cresswell, 2014). Data collection, measurement, and analysis procedures are laid forth in the study's scope and objectives. Robson and McCartan, (2016) assert that the stage of selecting the appropriate research design is the most crucial part of the research as this converts the research questions into a research project. This study is descriptive as it is conducted to ascertain the characteristics of Ghanaian women (Sekaran and Bougie 2016) and it is explanatory as it is focused on the phenomena which investigate the relationship between two or more variables (Saunders, et al, (2016). Thus, the researcher employed a descriptive survey design” in undertaking the investigation.

3.5 Research Approach

Research approach refers to the reasoning behind the research, the role played by the existing body of knowledge, and how data are collected. There are three general research approaches in the literature as found by scholars: abduction, deduction, and induction.

Researchers like Ponelis, (2015) and Saunders et al., (2016) posit that the inductive approach is synonymous with interpretivism, while the deductive approach is interchangeable with positivism. The inductive approach involves the collection of data to come up with a theory that is based on the data analysed (Collis and Hussey, 2013). On the other hand, a deductive approach entails testing a theory and

hypotheses for which a research strategy must be designed to test the hypothesis, which is ultimately confirmed, disproved, or modified (Gray, 2014). This research employed the deductive approach.

The abduction approach according to Suddaby, (2006) is the combination of induction and deductive approach. If a researcher wants to combine the deductive and inductive methods, an abduction approach may be the right choice.. Ponelis (2015) believe that if a researcher wants to conduct a phenomenal exploration, theme modification, or the modification of an existing theory, then the abduction approach is the best suited approach. For this study the researcher used the deductive research approach.

Table3.1

Deduction	Induction	Abduction
When the premises are true, the conclusion must also be true	Known premises are used to generate untested conclusions	Known premises are used to generate testable conclusions
Generalizing from the general to the specific	Generalizing from the specific to the general	Generalizing from the interactions between the specific and the general
Data collection is used to evaluate hypotheses for an existing theory	Data collection is used to explore a phenomenon, identify themes and create a conceptual framework	Data collection is used to explore a phenomenon, identify themes, locate these in a conceptual framework and test the results through subsequent data collection
Theory falsification or verification	Theory generation and building	Theory generation or modification, using existing theory where appropriate, to build a new or modify existing theory

Source: Ponelis (2015)

3.5 Research Methods

Struwig and Stead (2013), argued that two basic methodological techniques can be used in research: quantitative and qualitative. The use of qualitative or quantitative methods, or both, is dependent on the research field and goals (Dudovskiy, 2018). Quantitative research is deductive in its observation of the connection between research and theory, according to Struwig and Stead (2013), whereas qualitative research is inductive. Quantitative data collection is typically faster than qualitative data collection (Creswell and Creswell, 2018). As a result, it is more challenging to generalise the findings of qualitative researchers because they tend to investigate a smaller sample size. In light of the preceding arguments, the two methods are discussed in the following section.

3.5.1 Quantitative Approach

Quantitative analysis, as mentioned by Dudovskiy (2018), supports the unbiased and objective gathering of “measurable data from a large number of participants. The positivist foundations of quantitative research are rooted in the conviction that reality exists exactly as it is (Struwig and Stead, 2013). According to Struwig and Stead (2013), quantitative research aims to control and anticipate phenomena. Saunders et al. (2019), point out that the quantitative approach focuses on quantification and statistics in its data collecting and analysis. Struwig and Stead (2013), further noted that the quantitative research approach aids the researcher to react to questions on how a given decision has been taken. According to Boateng (2014), this strategy aims to assess the extent to which an issue exists or the link that exists between aspects of a phenomenon by measuring variations.” To avoid bias in data collection and analysis, the quantitative method is an invaluable tool for scientists and researchers.

However, Dudovskiy (2018), suggests that the limitation of quantitative research resides “in the fact that their analysis does not apply to particular circumstances. Aside from that, they are unable to shed light on specific research questions. This research employs a quantitative approach to data collection by administering a questionnaire to the study respondents.

3.5.2 Qualitative Approach

Qualitative analysis considers the data that has been gathered from the viewpoints of key informants in their natural setting, according to Ary et al, (2018). In-depth comprehension is another guarantee of qualitative research (Dudovskiy, 2018). “When compared to quantitative research, qualitative studies rely more on in-depth interviews and written descriptions of phenomena of interest, as opposed to cold, hard statistics (Struwig and Stead 2013). According to Wellman et al (2005), qualitative research is more of an approach than a design, and it incorporates post positivist and interpretative research paradigms that seek to explain and evaluate the meaning of occurrences in social environments, making it descriptive. Struwig and Stead (2013) characterise the goal of qualitative research as that of describing and analysing a phenomenon within its context to understand the meaning it conveys.

Dudovskiy (2018) identified five popular qualitative research designs that have been frequently used in public administration and corporate management research” (Struwig and Stead, 2013). Methods such as case studies, ethnographies, phenomenological analyses, grounded theory experiments, and content analyses are all included. By contrast, qualitative research allows for greater flexibility during the study (Ary et al, 2018). As opposed to the statistical analysis and numerical data used in quantitative methods, the more realistic impression of the search situation provided by qualitative research instruments is one of their primary advantages (Dudovskiy, 2018). The adoption of qualitative research methods has many benefits,

one of which is the increased comprehension of a research issue. Still, qualitative studies come with their fair share of drawbacks.

3.6 Research Strategy

For data gathering and analysis, a specific approach is employed for each research strategy. Because each approach has benefits and drawbacks, determining the best strategy is one of the research's key objectives (Yin, 2014). Some tactics are linked with the deductive approach, while others are with the inductive approach. Narrative, action research, grounded theory, ethnographies, case studies, and archive research are all examples of qualitative methods (Saunders et al., 2019; Gray, 2014). A quantitative method, on the other hand, is related to other strategies such as surveys and experiments (Creswell, 2014). For this study, the survey design is employed to accomplish the research objectives.

3.7 Population

The population of research, as explained by Saunders et al (2016), involves the total set of cases, more than just people, from which a sample is taken. Cooper and Schindler, (2014) assert that the population consists of a full list of elements and encompasses the “entire group of people, events, or things of interest” that are to be investigated (Struwig and Stead, 2013, p. 238). This specific group shares a particular set of characteristics (Collis and Hussey, 2014). According to Sekaran and Bougie (2016), the population of the research is the universal set, which is the entire list of elements, from which a sample is drawn. The population for this study was all Ghanaian women entrepreneurs in Greater Accra Region and Ashanti Region.

3.7.1 Sample

The subset of the population that serves as group of members that involves the element from which the researcher collects the data (Struwig and Stead, 2013). The basic idea of sampling is to include the entire population (Cooper and Schindler, 2014). The sample of this study was drawn from Ghanaian women entrepreneurs. The women entrepreneur was targeted as a subject for data collection as they were the most informed individuals in their business. Sekaran and Bougie, (2016) assert that “A subject is a single member of the sample, just as an element is a single member of the population”

3.7.2 Sample size

The sample size is the number of surveys for which data has been collected (Lavrakas, 2008). It is important to determine the required numbers of the sample before the process of collecting data. Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2016) stated that the larger sample size reduces the amount of error in generalising to the population. Hair et al. (2014) argued that the adequate minimum sample size is 100 responses to estimate the correlations between variables. The sample size of this research was one hundred and fifty (150). The researcher is of the view that this sample is a fair representation of the population of the study.”

3.7.3 Sampling

The notion of sampling in research, involves the practice of choosing a subset of respondents from the target population. The researcher selects some of people within the target population and obtains data from them. The researcher then generalises the result from this small number of population over the larger target population of the research (Du Plooy-Cilliers et al, 2014). Gravetter and Frozano (2012) explain that sampling is a technique that uses a small

sample of a population to draw conclusions about that group as a whole. Finding respondents who can provide information that is indicative of the behaviour or characteristics of the population is the aim of sample selection (Ary, Jacobs and Sorensen, 2010). There are two major categories of sampling strategies, according to Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2016): (a) Probability sample, and (b) non-probability sample. The likelihood of choosing each element as a sample subject is known as probability sampling (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). In other words, this sampling method uses random selection to choose the sample, giving each component a known chance of being chosen (Bryman and Bell, 2015).

Non-probability sampling, however, is the method used when it is unknown what factors will be chosen as sample subjects (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016). In nonprobability sampling, a sample is not selected by the random selection method, therefore, some elements are more likely to be selected as compared to others (Bryman and Bell, 2015). This sampling is good for quick surveys or when the researcher is unable to get access to the whole population (Walliman, 2011). This study adopts non-probability sampling. This method enabled the researcher to sample female entrepreneurs who could be conveniently reached for data collection.” Further, the convenience sampling technique enabled the researcher to select female entrepreneurs who had access to WhatsApp, Facebook Messenger, and Emails for administering the questionnaires.

Female entrepreneurs in the Greater Accra Region and Ashanti Region were captured in the study because the two regions are where most Ghanaian businesses are located and are also dominated by female entrepreneurs in Ghana. Further, the data on the female entrepreneurs in the regions were available. The researcher set out the parameters of inclusion of entrepreneurs as follows; all the firms should be in existence for at least a year, and every firm selected should be a properly registered firm which is located in either Greater Accra Region or Ashanti Region. A

firm qualifies for inclusion in the study if it is owned by a woman entrepreneur. All participants were aged 20 years and above. The researcher selected these participants from the membership list of the association of Ghana industries and a list of businesses provided by the National Board for Small-Scale Industries as well as the association of women entrepreneurs.

3.8 Data Collection Instruments

Secondary and primary sources were employed to obtain data for the research projects. Original reports, journal abstracts, scholarly books, and documents were the secondary data sources. The questionnaire was the main primary data-gathering tool. The choice of a research instrument, as explained by Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill (2019), is determined by the research's goal. Primary data was used for achieving the study objectives. Primary “data were gathered with the help of a questionnaire that was created based on a review of similar studies (see appendix1). The content of the questionnaire was adapted from Khan et al (2021), Namrata and Anita (2018) and Tambunan (2016) because these scholars carried out a research which was measuring similar variables as this research. The questionnaire was appropriate for the study because the study objectives were expected to produce numerical results capable of statistical analysis. Additionally, the questionnaire enabled the researcher to obtain standardised data from the respondents in answering the research questions relating to the dependent and independent variables (see table 3.0).

The questionnaire was made up of four sections. The first section solicited background information from the respondents. The second to fourth sections were structured to collect data related to the research objectives. The measurement scale was a five-point Likert Scale. The scale ratings were 5= Strongly Agree; 4=Agree; 3=Undecided; 2=Disagree; and 1= Strongly

Disagree. The questionnaire was designed in such a way that, they answered the below” questions:

1. What are the personal characteristics “that contribute to the entrepreneurial success of women” in Ghana?
2. What are the factors that contribute to “the entrepreneurial success of women” in Ghana?
3. What measures can be employed to “support the sustainability of female entrepreneurship” in Ghana?

Table 3.0: Dependent and Independent variables

Dependent variables	Independent variable
Personality traits (risk taken propensity, locus of control and need for achievement)	Entrepreneurial success of women
Competence	Entrepreneurial success of women
Demographic characteristics	Entrepreneurial success of women
Resource availability	Entrepreneurial success of women
External Opportunities	Entrepreneurial success of women

Source: author 2023

3.9 Data Collection Procedure

The female entrepreneurs were presented with an introductory letter by the researcher for data collection. The value of research ethics cannot be overstated. The research has been conducted with consideration of traditional ethical issues as pertained to social science research. Ethical consideration in this regard “refers to ethos or way of life and social norms for conduct that distinguish between acceptable and unacceptable behaviour (Collis and Hussey, 2014). In

this analysis, “the researcher followed human ethical guidelines, including informed consent, tolerance for anonymity and confidentiality, data storage and privacy. The researcher sought ethical approval from the School of business and creative industries, University of the West of Scotland (see appendix 4), which was sent to the participating women entrepreneurs to obtain their consent to conduct the study. All of the participants were issued informed consent forms to fill out and sign (see appendix 2). The researcher included them in the study based on their informed consent.”

The fieldwork was completed in three weeks period between February and March 2022. A typical response time to the questionnaire was anticipated to last 20 to 30 minutes. The questionnaire was administered through Google Forms. The email and WhatsApp accounts of the entrepreneurs were used for administering the questionnaires. These were obtained from “the database of the National Board for Small Scale Industries in Ghana and the association of Ghana industries. The link to the questionnaire was sent to them to fill out.” Follow-up calls were made to the women entrepreneurs who were delayed in responding to the questions for quick response.

3.10 Validity and Reliability

Validity and reliability improve transparency and reduce opportunities for researcher bias in science. Validity and dependability are crucial indicators in quantitative research, according to Maree (2016), but trustworthiness is more suited to qualitative research. If the same result can be reached by using the same instrument more than once in a given similar circumstance, then the validity and reliability of the research demonstrate that the research has conformed to scientific requirements (Dudovskiy, 2018). Sekaran and Bougie (2016) explain that “a thorough evaluation of reliability and validity for all secondary data includes an examination of the data collection

methods. It would be difficult to explain the impact of error margins on hypothesized relationships that are being evaluated without checking the research's reliability and validity.”

3.11 Validity

Research validity refers to the degree to which a study accurately measures or reflects what it claims to measure. In other words, research validity concerns whether the conclusions drawn from a study are based on accurate, reliable and relevant data (Van der Riet and Durrheim 2009). Validity is defined as adhering to research principles that are considered sound. These research principles should be able to help the researcher make specific deductions and inferences from the data in order draw conclusions from the analysis. Validity according to Van der Riet and Durrheim (2009) is the degree to which the conclusions drawn by the researcher are sound and informed by credible data so that the research can make specific generalizations of the result on the target population. Ponelis (2015) posits that criterion validity determines the extent to which a measure or test is related to an external criterion or standard. It assesses whether the results obtained from a measurement instrument align with other established measures or outcomes. The most basic type of validity is content validity which reflects how well a test represents the universe of elements from which it was created. A copy of the questionnaire was sent to the research supervisors to see whether the number and form of items in the questionnaire accurately measures the definition or construct of the instrument. Based on the supervisors' comments, the researcher made the changes required. The items were adopted or modified from international tools and literature to meet the study concepts and objectives.”

3.12 Reliability

In research, reliability deals with “the consistency of a measure in research, reliability is achieved when a specific approach is applied repeatedly to the same object and yields the same

result (Babbie and Mouton, 2004). In this research, Cronbach's Alpha was employed since it is the most often utilized reliability test when the Likert Scale is used to collect data (Dudovskiy, 2018). Cronbach's Alpha test was employed to verify the questionnaire's reliability”, according to Sekaran and Bougie (2016). Survey responses from female entrepreneurs reveal that the results are satisfactory. The reliability scale ranges from zero to one and reliability increases when the test score is near 1

3.13 Data Analysis

According to Babbie and Mouton (2004), the method of “data analysis involves the technique of assessing the identified patterns in the data obtained and making observations from it and comparing the observation with what other researchers have found. In the current research, the researcher organized the data and the inaccuracies discovered were eliminated. The data was coded and entered into the computer, and descriptive statistics were used to analyse it using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The data were categorized according to the many facets of the factors influencing the success of women entrepreneurs. In analysing the background information of the respondents, frequencies, percentages, and cross-tabulation were computed and represented in Tables. The research hypothesis was tested by using correlation and regression analysis. Descriptive statistics such as mean rankings and standard deviation were initially performed.” The multiple linear regression was then performed and presented for discussion.

3.14 Summary

This chapter outlined and justified the approach taken to collect and analyze data. This chapter provides a detailed account of the methods employed, the participants involved, and the instruments used to gather information. By clearly delineating the research process, this chapter

ensures that the study's findings are reliable, valid, and replicable. The chapter detailed the procedures used to select the participants or subjects. This section explains the sampling technique employed. Additionally, it specifies the inclusion and exclusion criteria that were applied to ensure the sample's relevance to the research objectives. The chapter outlined the data collection method employed. This section describes the instruments used in data collection, such as questionnaires and provides a rationale for their selection.

After data collection, the chapter elucidates the steps taken to analyse the gathered information. This includes a description of the statistical techniques employed to derive meaningful insights from the data. Furthermore, the chapter addresses the ethical considerations that were taken into account during the research process. This includes obtaining informed consent from participants, safeguarding their confidentiality, and adhering to ethical guidelines outlined by relevant the University. In conclusion, the methodology chapter serves as a roadmap for the research study, providing a comprehensive account of the methods, participants, and instruments used. By detailing the research design, participant selection, data collection and analysis procedures, ethical considerations, and limitations, this chapter ensures the reliability, validity, and replicability of the study's finding

CHAPTER FOUR

ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

4.0 Introduction

The results of the data collected through questionnaire administration have been presented in this chapter. The data have been analysed, synthesized and discussed in comparison

with what has been discussed in the literature. The data obtained through Google Forms were exported to Microsoft Excel. The data were checked for completeness and irrelevant fields were deleted. This was done by reorganizing and regrouping the raw data to make meaning out of it. Classified data were arranged into a logical order by the use of Microsoft Excel and imported to the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive statistics were run and the results were presented in the form of tables, figures, charts, and text. Correlation and regression analysis were done to determine the relationship between the variables of the study. The results were discussed and compared to previous studies on the subject to draw meaningful conclusions.

4.1 Analysis of response

The researcher conducted a survey among Ghanaian women who are entrepreneurs in Ghana. The enterprises were obtained from the database of the Association for Ghana Industries, NBSSI and association of women entrepreneurs. The selected businesses also recommended “other businesses run by women entrepreneurs in Ghana. The women entrepreneurs were contacted via emails and WhatsApp seeking their permission to answer the questionnaires.” The questionnaire was administered to the women entrepreneurs to obtain responses. The responses were received through Emails, WhatsApp, and Facebook Messenger. The responses obtained were checked for completeness and incomplete responses were eliminated. In all, 162 responses were received. After downloading the data and scrutinizing it, 12 representing 7% were found to be incomplete. The incomplete responses were rejected and 150 responses representing 93% were accepted for further analysis. Therefore, a total of one hundred and fifty questionnaires passed the quality test and were used in the analysis.

Figure 4.1: Questionnaire response

4.2 Validity and Reliability

Table 4.1 shows the reliability test for the data collection tool used for soliciting data for the study. “Cronbach's Alpha was employed since it is the most often utilized reliability test when the Likert Scale is used to collect data (Khalid and Kumar, 2012). Cronbach’s alpha coefficient measures the internal consistency, or reliability, of a set of survey items. It helps determine whether a collection of items consistently measures the same characteristic. Cronbach’s alpha quantifies the level of agreement on a standardized 0 to 1 scale. Higher values indicate higher agreement between items.

According to Sekaran and Bougie (2016), high Cronbach’s alpha values indicate that response values for each participant across a set of questions are consistent. For example, when participants give a high response for one of the items, they are also likely to provide high responses for the other items. This consistency indicates the measurements are reliable and the

items might measure the same characteristic. Cronbach's Alpha test was employed to verify the questionnaire's reliability, according to Sekaran and Bougie (2016). Survey responses from female entrepreneurs reveal that results are satisfactory. The reliability scale ranges from zero to one and reliability increases when the test score is near 1. The results show Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.919 for the personality variable and 0.968 for competence. The reliability value obtained for demographics was 0.929 and the value for the opportunity variable was 0.731. Resources availability and entrepreneurial success had Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.973. Since all the values are greater than .7 and closer to 1, it can be concluded that the data collection instrument was reliable.”

Table 4. 1: Validity and Reliability Test

Personality Traits	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.919	5
Competence	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.968	6
Demographics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.929	5
Opportunity	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.731	5
Resources	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.808	6
Entrepreneurial success	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.973	9

4.3 Background Information

Information regarding the background characteristics of the research respondents was captured in the first section of the questionnaire. The information was to give an idea of the category of female entrepreneurs who participated in the research. It was also essential to the initial context for the understanding of the main analysis which follows this section. Data was obtained concerning age, highest “level of education, number of years in business, work status of entrepreneur, number of employees, and average annual income. Age and educational qualification were obtained to gain an understanding of the personal characteristics of the female entrepreneurs. Number of years in business, work status of entrepreneur, number of employees and average annual income were business-related information necessary to have an idea of the experiences of the female entrepreneurs and progress of their businesses over the years.” The results have been presented in Table 4.2.

Table 4. 2: Age of Respondents

Age of Respondent	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
20 – 30 years	49	32.7	32.7
31 – 40 years	52	34.7	67.3
41 – 50 years	19	12.7	80.0
51 – 60 years	13	8.7	88.7
Above 60 years	17	11.3	100.0

Source: Field Survey (2022)

Figure 4. 2: Age of Respondents
Source: Field Survey (2022)

The age categories of the women entrepreneurs are represented in Table 4.2 and Figure 4.2. The results show that, most of the female entrepreneurs who participated in the study were between the ages of 31 and 40 years (34.7%). This was followed by respondents between 20 to 30 who were (32.7) and those between 41 to 50 years, represented by 12.7%. The respondents above 60 years were 11.3% while those between 50 and 60 years of age were 8.7% of the total respondents. The results suggest that most of the respondents were in their middle ages, typically between 20 and 40 years of age.”

Table 4. 3: Highest Level of Education

Highest Level of Education	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
No Formal Education	7	4.7	4.7
High School & below	8	5.3	10.0
Diploma	17	11.3	21.3

First Degree	72	48.0	69.3
Master's Degree	46	30.7	100.0
Total	150	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2022)

Figure 4. 3: Highest Level of Education

Source: Field Survey (2022)

Results presented in Table 4.3 and Figure 4.3 show that most of the female entrepreneurs (48%) had First Degree as their highest educational qualification. Other qualifications noted were master's degree (30.7%), Diploma (11.3%), and High school qualification (5.3%). Only 4.7% of the respondents did not have formal education. The results suggest that the female entrepreneurs had high educational qualifications up to the master's level.

Table 4. 4: Number of Years in Business

Number of years in business	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Below 1 year	50	33.3	33.3

1 – 5 years	13	8.7	42.0
6 – 10 years	65	43.3	85.3
Above 10 years	22	14.7	100
Total	150	100	

Source: Field Survey (2022)

Figure 4. 4: Number of Years in Business

Source: Field Survey (2022)

From Table 4.4 and Figure 4.4, most of the entrepreneurs have been in business for 6 to 10 years. The entrepreneurs who have been in business for less than 1 year were 33.3%. The entrepreneurs who have operated their businesses for more than 10 years were 14.7% with only 8.7% who have been in business between 1 and 5 years.

Table 4. 5: Work status of entrepreneur

Work Status of Entrepreneur	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Full time	77	51.3	51.3
Part-time	73	48.7	100.0
Total	150	100	

Source: Field Survey (2022)

Figure 4. 5: Number of Years in Business

Source: Field Survey (2022)

From Table 4.4 and Figure 4.4, “more than half (51.3%) of the female entrepreneurs were full-time entrepreneurs. The remaining 48.7% of the entrepreneurs were part-time workers. It can be deduced from the results that; most women entrepreneurs engage in their businesses on a full-time basis.”

Table 4. 6: Number of Employees

Number of Employees	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Less than 10 employees	88	58.7	58.7
10 - 20 employees	12	8.0	66.7
21 – 50 employees	46	30.7	97.4

Above 50 employees	4	2.6	100.0
Total	150	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2022)

Figure 4. 6: Number of Employees
Source: Field Survey (2022)

Results from Table 4.6 and Figure 4.6 indicate that majority (58.7%) of the entrepreneurs, had employees less than 10 in their businesses. The businesses with employee strength between 21 and 50 were 30.7%, followed by businesses with 10 to 20 employees represented by 8%. Only 2.6% of the businesses had employee strength above 50.

Table 4. 7: Annual income of respondents

Average annual income	Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
less than \$10, 000	78	52.0	52.0
\$ 10, 000 – \$49, 999	31	20.7	72.7

\$ 50, 000 – \$99, 999	25	16.7	89.4
\$ 100,000 and above	16	10.6	100.0
Total	150	100.0	

Source: Field Survey (2022)

Figure 4. 7: Annual income of respondent
Source: Field Survey (2022)

On the earning capacity of the female entrepreneurs, Table 4.7 and Figure 4.7 show that majority (52%) earn an average annual income of less than \$10, 000. Entrepreneurs who earn \$ 10, 000 – \$49, 999 annually were 20.7% followed by those who earn \$ 50, 000 to \$99, 999 annually, represented by 16.7. Female entrepreneurs who earn above \$ 100,000 and above on average were 10.6%. The results suggest that the average income of the female entrepreneurs is within the lower bracket of \$10, 000.

4.3.1 Cross-tabulation of Background Information

Cross tabulation was done to compare education level, age, work status, annual income, and number of years in business. This was necessary to determine how the demographic factors influence each other and for that matter the success of the women entrepreneurs.

Table 4. 8: Percentage distribution by Age and Education

			Age					Total
			20 - 30 years	31-40 years	41-50 years	51-60 years	Above 60 years	
Highest level of education	Diploma	Count	4	0	0	13	0	17
		% within Education.	23.5%	0.0%	0.0%	76.5%	0.0%	100.0%
		% Age	8.2%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%	0.0%	11.3%
	First Degree	Count	33	31	2	0	6	72
		% within Education	45.8%	43.1%	2.8%	0.0%	8.3%	100.0%
		% within Age	67.3%	59.6%	10.5%	0.0%	35.3%	48.0%
High School and below	Count	8	0	0	0	0	8	
		% within Education	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Age	16.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	5.3%
Masters Degree	Count	4	21	17	0	4	46	
		% within Education	8.7%	45.7%	37.0%	0.0%	8.7%	100.0%
		% within Age	8.2%	40.4%	89.5%	0.0%	23.5%	30.7%

	No	Formal	Count	0	0	0	0	7	7
	Education	%	within Education	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		%	within Age	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	41.2%	4.7%
Total		Count		49	52	19	13	17	150
		%	within Education	32.7%	34.7%	12.7%	8.7%	11.3%	100.0%
		%	Age	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Field Survey (2022)

The study sought to compare the various age groups of the female entrepreneurs and their highest level of education. Cross tabulation was done and presented in Table 4.8. From the results, out of the 17 entrepreneurs who had Diploma qualifications, most (76.5%) were between the ages of 51 to 60 years. Further, the respondents with First Degree were mostly (45.8%) between the ages of 20 to 30 years followed by 31 to 40 years. A great majority (89.5%) of the female entrepreneurs who had master's degree were between 41 to 50 years of age. The results indicate that, the majority of the female entrepreneurs had First Degree as their highest educational qualification and were aged 20 to 30 years. This finding is in tandem with that of Tlais and Kauser (2019), who revealed that a population that is disproportionately youthful, is essential to the economic health of a country, which is the case in Ghana. The impact of an entrepreneur's age, religion, gender, background, and education, as well as their level of experience and education, has been well documented in numerous studies such as Welmilla et al (2011).

Table 4. 9: Work Status and Average Annual Income

Work Status* Average Annual Income Crosstabulation		
	Average Annual Income	Total

			\$ 10,000 - \$ 50,000	\$ 51,000 - \$ 100,000	Above 100,000	\$less than \$10,000	
Work Status	Full time	Count	24	25	16	12	77
		% within Work Status	31.2%	32.5%	20.8%	15.6%	100.0%
		% within Average annual income	77.4%	100.0%	100.0%	15.4%	51.3%
Part time	Count	Count	7	0	0	66	73
		% within Work Status	9.6%	0.0%	0.0%	90.4%	100.0%
		% within Average annual income	22.6%	0.0%	0.0%	84.6%	48.7%
Total	Count	Count	31	25	16	78	150
		% within Work Status	20.7%	16.7%	10.7%	52.0%	100.0%
		% within Average annual income	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Field Survey (2022)

Table 4.9 shows cross-tabulation for work status and average annual income of the female entrepreneurs. From the results, a great majority (90.4%) of the part-time female entrepreneurs earn below \$10,000 as compared to 15.6% of the full-time entrepreneurs who earn below \$10,000. The results suggest that the female entrepreneurs who engage in full-time work earn more for their companies than those who engage in part-time work.

Table 4. 10: Age and Number of years in business

Number of years in business * Age Crosstabulation										
			Age							
			20-30	31-40	41-50	51-60	Above 60	Total		
Years in business	in 1 - 5 years	Count	12	1	0	0	0	13		
		% within Years in business	92.3%	7.7%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%		
		% within Age	24.5%	1.9%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	8.7%		

	6 - 10 years	Count	4	31	17	13	0	65
		% within Years in business	6.2%	47.7%	26.2%	20.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Age	8.2%	59.6%	89.5%	100.0%	0.0%	43.3%
	Above 10 years	Count	0	20	2	0	0	22
		% within Years in business	0.0%	90.9%	9.1%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Age	0.0%	38.5%	10.5%	0.0%	0.0%	14.7%
	Below 1 year	Count	33	0	0	0	17	50
		% within Years in business	66.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	34.0%	100.0%
		% within Age	67.3%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%	33.3%
Total		Count	49	52	19	13	17	150
		% within Years in business	32.7%	34.7%	12.7%	8.7%	11.3%	100.0%
		% within Age	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Field Survey (2022)

A comparison of the age of the female entrepreneurs and the number of years in business were made and the result is presented in Table 4.10. According to the results, out of the 65 entrepreneurs who have been in business for 6 to 10 years, 47.7% of them were between 31 to 40 years. Moreover, for 50 entrepreneurs who have been in business for less than a year, 66.0% were between the ages of 20 to 30 years. It can be deduced from the results that, the female entrepreneurs start their businesses between 20 to 30 years and grow them thereafter.

Table 4.11: Number of Employees and Average Annual Income

		Average annual income * Number of Employees Crosstabulation					
		Number of Employees					
			10- 20	21 - 50	Above 50	less than 10	Total
Average annual income	\$ 10, 000 - \$ 50, 000	Count	4	19	4	4	31
		% within Average annual income	12.9%	61.3%	12.9%	12.9%	100.0%
		% within Employees Number	33.3%	41.3%	100.0%	4.5%	20.7%
	\$ 51, 000 -	Count	0	25	0	0	25

	\$100,000	% within Average annual income	0.0%	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%
		% within Employees Number	0.0%	54.3%	0.0%	0.0%	16.7%
	Above 100,000	\$Count	0	0	0	16	16
		% within Average annual income	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%	100.0%
		% within Number of Employees	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	18.2%	10.7%
	less than \$10, 000	\$Count	8	2	0	68	78
		% within Average annual income	10.3%	2.6%	0.0%	87.2%	100.0%
		% within Number of Employees	66.7%	4.3%	0.0%	77.3%	52.0%
Total		Count	12	46	4	88	150
		% within Average annual income	8.0%	30.7%	2.7%	58.7%	100.0%
		% within Number of Employees	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Source: Field Survey (2022)

Crosstabulation of the number of employees and average annual income of the female entrepreneurs is presented in Table 4.11. The results show that, out of the companies earning \$ 10, 000 - \$ 50, 000 annually, 61.3% had employees numbering 21 to 50. Further, the female entrepreneurs with average annual income of \$ 51, 000 - \$100, 000 had 54.3% of employee size of 21 to 50. The results suggest that, the most of the female entrepreneurs had average employee size of 21 to 50 and earned less than \$ 10, 000 - \$ 50, 000 annually, on average.

4.4 Descriptive Statistics

This section of the analysis presents the descriptive statistics of the variables for the study. The variables discussed under the section are the competence of female entrepreneurs, the personality of female entrepreneurs, demographics, opportunity, resources, and success determinants of the female entrepreneurs. Descriptive statistics presented are the mean, standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis. The results have been presented in Table 4.12.”

Table 4. 12: Descriptive statistics of variables

Descriptive Statistics							
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Skewness		Kurtosis	
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic	Std. Error
Competence	150	3.6622	1.21357	-1.283	.198	.225	.394
Personality	150	3.4640	1.15586	-.991	.198	.053	.394
Demographics	150	3.4000	1.13587	-.917	.198	-.009	.394
Success	150	3.2830	1.12602	-.618	.198	-.137	.394
Opportunity	150	2.3627	.78489	-.018	.198	-.612	.394
Resources	150	2.0378	.61855	.950	.198	2.622	.394
Valid (listwise)	N 150						

Source: Field Data, 2022

Results from Table 4.12 show that the competence of female entrepreneurs had the highest mean. The mean obtained was 3.6622 with a standard deviation of 1.21357. A negative skewed value of -1.283 is recorded. The results suggest that the average female entrepreneur has the competence to be successful in their businesses. The mean result for personality

characteristics of female entrepreneurs is 3.4640 and a standard deviation of 1.15586. The mean for demographics of female entrepreneurs' variables was 3.4000 and a standard deviation of 1.13587. The results suggest that the personality and demographics of the average female entrepreneur support them to be a success in their businesses. A negative skewed value of -.917 was recorded. Further analysis shows mean for female entrepreneur success variable of 3.2830, Opportunity (mean = 2.3627), and resources (mean = 2.0378). The mean for the female entrepreneurs' success variable shows that the average female entrepreneur in Ghana is successful in her business. The mean for the availability of opportunities (mean = 2.3627), and resources (mean = 2.0378) suggest minimal opportunities resources for the female entrepreneurs. Similar results were reported by Ummah and Gunapalan (2012) by showing family background (mean = 3.08), personality components (mean = 3.26), Institutional support (mean = 2.5), and business success (mean = 3.2). The authors concluded that the family background, the personality of female entrepreneurs, and institutional support averagely support the female entrepreneurs.

4.5 Correlation Analysis

The researcher correlated the analysis in order to ascertain the relationship between the independent and dependent variables of the study. The independent variables were personality trait, competence, demographics, external opportunity and resource availability. The dependent variable of the study was women success. The correlation analysis is presented in Table 4.13 below.

Correlations		Personality	Competence	Demographics	Opportunity	Resources	Success	
Spearman's rho	Personality	Correlation Coefficient	1.000					
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.					
		N	150					
	Competence	Correlation Coefficient	.382**	1.000				
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.				
		N	150	150				
	Demographics	Correlation Co.	.779**	.593**	1.000			
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.			
		N	150	150	150			
	Opportunity	Correlation Coefficient	.497**	.437**	.530**	1.000		
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.		
		N	150	150	150	150		
	Resources	Correlation Coefficient	.396**	.464**	.419**	.509**	1.000	
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.	
		N	150	150	150	150	150	
	Success	Correlation Coefficient	.786**	.360**	.567**	.453**	.244**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.062	.000	.003	.
		N	150	150	150	150	150	150

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4. 13: Correlation Matrix for study variables

Source: Field Data, 2022

Table 4.13 “shows the correlation matrix for all the variables of the study. These are personality traits, competence, demographics, opportunity, resources, and female entrepreneurs’ success. The results show significant positive influence of female entrepreneurs’ personality traits and success of their business ($r = .786^{**}$, $P = 0.000$). There was also a significant positive influence of competence of the women and their success in business ($r = .360^{**}$, $P = 0.000$). Demographic characteristics of the women showed insignificant influence on the women success ($r = .567^{**}$, $P = 0.062$). The personality of female entrepreneurs was found to influence the success of female entrepreneurs more than the competence of the women entrepreneurs. The results depict that, the internal factors, personality traits and competence of women strongly influence their business success while the demographic characteristics of the women do not. Ummah and Gunapalan (2012), concluded that, entrepreneurial success is strongly linked to a person's personality.

Further analysis shows that, external opportunities significantly influence the success of women entrepreneurs ($r = .453^{**}$, $P = 0.000$) while resources availability do not significantly influence the women success ($r = .244^{**}$, $P = 0.003$). Khan et al. (2021) made similar observations in their research that, there is a substantial positive link between the performance of women entrepreneurs and economic factors ($r = 0.522$, $P=0.001$), as well as socio-cultural elements ($r = 0.41$, $P=0.05$)”.

4.6 Regression Analysis

The linear multiple regression was used to present the results for the study. The hypothesis for the study were:

H₀₁: Personality traits of women “do not have a significant impact on the success of Ghanaian women entrepreneurs in Ghana.”

H₁: Personality traits of women “have a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

H₀₂: Competency of women entrepreneurs “do not have a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

H₂: Competency of women entrepreneurs “have a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

H₀₃: Demographic characteristics “do not have a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

H₃: Demographic characteristics “have a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

H₀₄: External Opportunities “do not have a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

H₄: External Opportunities “have a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

H₀₅: Resource availability “do not have a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

H₅: Resource availability “have a significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs” in Ghana.

4.6.1 Functional Equation

The model for multiple linear regression is given “as

$$y_i = \alpha + \beta_1 X_{i1} + \beta_2 X_{i2} + \beta_3 X_{i3} \dots \dots \dots \beta_p X_{ip} + \Sigma_i \text{for } i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n \dots \dots \dots 1$$

The regression model for the study is presented as:

$$FES = \alpha + \beta_1 PERS + \beta_2 COMP + \beta_3 DEM + \beta_4 OPP + \beta_5 RES + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots 2$$

Where:

FES_t = Female Entrepreneurs Success

PERS = Personality Traits

COMP = Competence

DEM = Demography

OPP = External Opportunities

RES = Resource Availability

ε_{it} = error term for the model”

Considering the results of the t-test and R², Adj. R² values for each independent variable in the function, the robustness of this model was assessed. Linear regression is robust to violations of normality assumptions, especially in large samples. The central limit theorem states that the distribution of the regression coefficients becomes normal as the sample size increases, even if the underlying variables are not normally distributed (Stine, 1989). The level of auto-correlation between the dependent and explanatory variables was determined using Durbin Watson statistics. For the following reasons, the Likert Scale's data were analysed using the

regression technique: the sample size (150) is sufficient (Jamieson, 2004). When analysing Likert scale, “parametric tests can be used to analyse data from Likert scales since they are sufficiently resilient to produce generally unbiased results that are acceptable and close to the truth” (Sullivan and Artino 2013).

4.6.2 Hypothesis Testing

H_0 is usually rejected when its probability falls below the standard statistical threshold for rejecting it, which is called the significance level (p-value) in statistical hypothesis (Creswell, 2014). Hypotheses are examined at a 5% confidence level (= 0.05) in this research. The hypothesis was either rejected or accepted as shown in Table 4.10.

Table 4. 14: Test for Hypothesis

Variable	Hypothesis	P- Value	$\alpha = 0.05$	Decision	Decision
				H_0	H_A
Personality Traits with Women success	H_{01}, H_{11}	.000	0.05	Reject	Accept
Competence with Women Success	H_{02}, H_{22}	.000	0.05	Reject	Accept
Demographics with Women Success	H_{03}, H_{33}	.736	0.05	Accept	Reject
External Success with Women Success	H_{04}, H_{44}	.557	0.05	Accept	Reject
Resource Availability with Women Success	H_{05}, H_{55}	.000	0.05	Reject	Accept

Source: Field Data, 2022

Table 4.14 shows the test for the hypothesis of the study. Based on the result, the study rejects the null hypothesis (H_{01} , H_{02} , H_{05}) since the probability values are less than the alpha value of 0.05. The alternate hypothesis (H_1 , H_2 , H_5) were accepted. Further, the study accepts the null hypothesis (H_{03} , H_{04}) since the probability values are greater than the alpha value of 0.05. The alternate hypothesis (H_3 , H_4) were rejected. The results suggest that, personality traits, competence and the availability of resources to women entrepreneurs significantly impact their success. On the other hand, the demographic characteristics and external opportunities do not significantly impact the success of women entrepreneurs in Ghana.

4.6.3 Multiple Regression

Table 4. 15: Multiple Regression

		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Durbin-Watson =	
R=.273		R ² =.751		Adjusted Square = .422		R = 1.731 F=2.321	
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.	
1	(Constant)	3.377	.257		13.126	.000	
	Personality trait	.073	.080	.097	.914	.000	
	Competence	.073	.111	.177	.655	.000	
	Demography	-.042	.123	.090	.338	.736	
	Ext. Opportunity	-.154	.074	-.235	-2.085	.557	
	Resources	.124	.083	.131	-1.497	.000	

a. Dependent Variable: Success

Source: Field Data, 2022

The F statistics which is a test of significance for the entire regression is shown as 2.321 “with probability value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05. The results shows that, the regression is

statistically significant because $p\text{-value} = 0.000 < 0.05$. The results suggest that, when female entrepreneurs have resources, and are competent combined with their personality traits they are able to succeed in their businesses. However, demographics and external opportunities are found not to influence the success of the female entrepreneurs significantly. Field (2009) warns that values of less than one or more than three for Durbin-Watson is a serious problem. Test statistic levels in the 1.5 to 2.5 range are considered to be normal under Durbin-Watson. To be on the safe side, researchers should keep an eye on values that fall outside of this range. The results show a value of 1.731 which falls within the normal range thereby confirming model fitness for the study. The overall model explains the research's compatibility with the model. This may be seen in the R^2 . This coefficient represents the degree to which the regression equation accurately predicts the observed data.

The model summary show an Adjusted R Square value of .422 which means that, personality traits, competencies, demographic characteristics, external opportunities and resource availability contribute 42.2% to the success of women entrepreneurs. The results suggest that, there is an unexplained 57.8% other factors that influence female entrepreneurs success. The findings of Chong (2012) corroborate the findings of this study. Features such as talents of women and business knowledge, the usage of expert advisors, and his or her financial situation influence their success as noted by Chong (2012). Women success in Saudi Arabia is not influenced by personal or social networks, according to Iftikhar (2011). Comparatively, Kubickova and Prochazka (2014) viewed external environmental factors such as political, economic, and socio-cultural factors, as well as technology to influence women entrepreneurs' success.”

4.8 Summary

This research focused on examining the factors that contribute to women's entrepreneurial success in Ghana. The study aims to shed light on the key determinants that enable women entrepreneurs to thrive in a predominantly male-dominated business environment and provide insights for policymakers and stakeholders to create a conducive ecosystem for women's entrepreneurship. A sample of 150 women entrepreneurs from various industries Greater Accra and Ashanti regions in Ghana was selected, and surveys were administered to gather quantitative information on their businesses, access to resources, opportunities, demographics and levels of support received.

In the current chapter, the researcher “presented the results of the data collected from the field. The results were presented using descriptive and inferential statistics. The study confirmed two hypothesis and rejected three. The personality traits of women entrepreneurs, their competency in managing their businesses and availability of resources significantly influence their success. However, the demographics of female entrepreneurs such as age, education were found not to influence their success. External opportunities for the women entrepreneurs were also found not to influence their success. The next chapter presents the discussions and interpretations of the research findings. The summary shows that personality traits, competencies, demographic characteristics, external opportunities and resource availability contribute 42.2% to the success of women entrepreneurs. The results suggest that, there is an unexplained 57.8% other factors that influence female entrepreneurs success

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION AND INTERPRETATION OF FINDINGS

5.0 Introduction

This section of the thesis discusses and interprets the findings of the research in comparison with findings from previous scholars as reviewed in the literature. The discussions have been centred on the objectives of the study which sought to establish the correlation between the independent variables and the dependent variable: the relationship between personality traits, competency, demographic characteristics, external opportunities, resource availability and the success of women entrepreneurs in Ghana.

5.1 Impact of personality traits on the success of women entrepreneurs in Ghana

The study found in the previous chapter that the personality traits of women entrepreneurs significantly impact their success. These traits include the desire to take more risks, control their businesses, determination to improve upon their performance and the desire to take strict decisions for the business. Women's entrepreneurial success, according to Guicui and Xingyuan (2012), may be attributed to six different factors: personalities, human capital, femininity, entrepreneurial motivation, the entrepreneurial environment, and the nature of the start-up itself. The findings of Makhbul and Hasun (2011) that the entrepreneurs' independence, their ability to make their own decisions and their ability to control the organisations contribute to their success corroborate with the findings of this study. Cabrera and Mauricio (2017) found that, there are a variety of elements that influence the success of female entrepreneurs at every stage of the entrepreneurial process. Singh et al. (2013) also confirmed that innovation, futuristic

mind set, risk taking ability, adaptability and commitment have an impact on the success of entrepreneurs which is in tandem with the findings of this research.”

These factors can be located and organised at the “individual, micro, meso, and macro environmental levels. Human capital, education, and experience, as well as access to resources, are the most commonly cited factors in the literature reviewed, both at the internal and micro-environment levels. Balance, determination and resilience, were identified by Banda (2018) to contribute to the success of women entrepreneurs.” Individuals who are self-assured have a strong affinity for, value, and devote time and effort to, a particular activity. Dominance, Steadiness, Compliance, Influence and Resilience were the five personality traits of female entrepreneurs investigated by Sambul (2019). To be successful, female entrepreneurs needed to show dominance as their primary personality feature. Influence and Compliance were the other personality traits that were secondary in importance.

5.2 Impact of competency on the success of women entrepreneurs in Ghana

From the analysis, the findings showed that, competency of women entrepreneurs significantly impact their success. These include the skills to manage the business, the ability to select right management teams, “ability to generate new ideas and the ability to develop new products and services to meet customer demands. Competencies in the areas of staff development and the skill to bond well with teams to drive business success are also critical in the success of the women entrepreneurs. Raheem (2013) found that, individual competencies such as business management and leadership skills are critical for women success. Raheem (2013) elaborated that women are more likely to aspire to entrepreneurial success and believe that they have the capacity, capabilities, and aptitude for female company ownership in countries where society recognizes this. women entrepreneurs have a higher propensity than males to see

starting their own business as a rewarding and fulfilling endeavour, but a lack of positive perceptions about their inherent abilities and dispositions to do so, as well as a lack of personal interactions with other female entrepreneurs, hamper their progress. Schneider (2016) found that, in Germany and Ireland, women entrepreneurs have six first-order factors that can be used to assess their entrepreneurial abilities: functional task-related managerial skills, entrepreneurial characteristic adaptations of self-efficacy, risk-taking and innovation orientations, and the founder and innovator identity.”

5.3 Impact of demographic characteristics on the success of women entrepreneurs in Ghana

Findings from Chapter 4 of the study showed that, demographic characteristics of women entrepreneurs do not significantly impact their success. The “age of the women entrepreneurs as well as the educational qualification do not have substantial impact on the success of their businesses. The marital status and the performance of home duties of the women do not affect the success of the women entrepreneurs. The findings suggest that, women entrepreneurs do not succeed based on the fact that, they are women with associated duties of a woman. The findings of Tlais and Kauser (2019) discovered that patriarchal social norms, gender roles, and expectations, as well as societal expectations of women's domestic responsibilities and childbearing roles, all have a part in limiting women's entrepreneurial development and success. This is in disagreement with the observations of this study. Sajilan et al. (2015) indicated that, the impact of an entrepreneur's demographic features on their business changes depending on the situation. Women entrepreneurs are crucial to a company's development because they possess a unique set of traits like a strong demand for accomplishment, a high need for knowledge, and an internal locus of control. They stand out from those who aren't self-employed due to these traits.

In Dhaka, Amin (2021) demonstrated a link between demographic factors and the long-term success of women business owners. Among the demographic factors affecting the success of female business owners in Dhaka,” the proportion of the population with a college degree was found to be a strong one.

5.4 Impact of external opportunities on the success of women entrepreneurs in Ghana

The findings of the study showed that, external opportunities do not significantly impact “the success of women entrepreneurs. These include laws and regulations, coaching from Governmental and non-Governmental Organisations and relieves and tax incentives. According to Kalyani and Mounika (2016), women's motivations for starting their own businesses go beyond the traditional norms of financial gain, employment independence, personal growth, and well-being. Entrepreneurship is frequently fuelled by a sense of opportunity presented by a shifting environment. Their backgrounds are just as diverse as the reasons for beginning a business; some out of financial necessity, others out of a desire to use their free time in a profitable way, and yet others because they were inspired by a new idea. From the development of relevant business methods and skills to financial backing and access to credit, marketing and administration of women's microenterprises are heavily reliant on external support.

Bugawa and Aljuwaisri (2021) established Internal (personal) factors such as goals, motives, entrepreneurial orientation and human capital; and external (environmental) factors such as cultural, economic, legal, administrative and time management to influence the performance of women entrepreneurs. Female entrepreneurs' success is boosted by both sets of factors. In a consistent manner, Khan et al. (2021) established that women-owned businesses benefit from a combination of internal and external factors that contribute to their success. Internal factors include a desire for accomplishments, willingness to take risks, and confidence in

one's own abilities". The external factors on the other hand include economic and sociocultural factors.

5.5 Impact of resource availability on the success of women entrepreneurs in Ghana

The study found that the availability of resources to women entrepreneurs have significant impact on their success. Access to funding for the business, equipment and qualified labour are important for the success of women businesses. Further access to loans and land for business operations are crucial for the women entrepreneurs. This finding agrees with Rani and Hashim (2017). In their study on the success of women entrepreneurs, Rani and Hashim (2017) mentioned human capital, networking, financial aids, and opportunity as some of the influences that have positive impact on success of women entrepreneurs.

Research suggests that four factors determine the success of female entrepreneurs: access to resources, a need for achievement, a willingness to take risks, a strong sense of self-worth, and a creative and imaginative spirit. Social capital, human capital, and reputational capital were all found to be key contributors to the growth of women-owned enterprises by Sallah and Caesar (2020). The study also found that social capital, reputational capital, and human capital all have a favourable and significant effect on the success of women entrepreneurs. Adom (2015) admonishes that financial institutions and government agencies should develop targeted programs to provide women entrepreneurs with access to affordable credit, grants, and venture capital. Additionally, financial literacy programs can help women entrepreneurs make informed financial decisions and manage their businesses effectively

5.6 Summary

The purpose of this chapter is to provide a comprehensive discussion and interpretation of the findings obtained from the research on success factors of women entrepreneurs in Ghana. The study aimed to identify the key factors that contribute to the success of women entrepreneurs. The researcher presented the discussions of the findings of the study by comparing them with previous studies of scholars. The success factors for women entrepreneurs in Ghana are multifaceted and interconnected. Personality traits, access to resources and opportunities, government support and policies, all play a significant role in shaping the success of women entrepreneurs. By understanding and addressing these factors, policymakers and practitioners can create an enabling environment that empowers women entrepreneurs and contributes to Ghana's economic growth and development.

The findings corroborates with some past studies whiles other findings disagree with some previous studies. The study found that personality traits like risk taken propensity, need for achievement and locus of control have positive impact on entrepreneurial success of women. Again competence of women entrepreneurs as well their access to resources also significantly impact the success of women entrepreneurs in Ghana. It also came to light that demographic characteristics of women do not significantly affect the entrepreneurial success of Ghanaian women. The main findings established in the research and contributions of the research to industry and knowledge are presented in the next chapter. Finally, the limitations of the study and recommendations for further research are presented at the latter part of the chapter.

CHAPTER SIX

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.0 Introduction

The research, in this chapter, contains the conclusion and recommendations made regarding the findings of the study. The first section of the chapter captures a recap of the purpose of the study, the objectives of the research and the adopted methodology that facilitated the realisation of the objectives of the study. A summary of the research findings, research contributions and recommendations are further presented in the current chapter. The latter part of the chapter presents the recommendations for further action, limitations and conclusions for the study.

6.1 Purpose of this Research

The goal of the current research was to critically investigate the elements that influence Ghanaian women's business success. This study adds to our understanding of Ghanaian women entrepreneurs' achievements. According to Dzisi (2008), there has not been a lot of research on women's entrepreneurial success in developing nations, specifically Ghana. The research aims to close this gap in the body of knowledge. Five aspects of women entrepreneurs in Ghana were examined to achieve this: their personal traits, demographics, opportunities and resources from outside sources, competencies, and finally, their successes.

6.2 Summary of Findings

The main findings of the study were grouped under “personal success factors and external success factors. It came to light that, the personality traits and the competency level of women entrepreneurs significantly impact their success of women entrepreneurs have substantial

impact on their success. the research further indicated that the availability of resources to women entrepreneurs have significant impact on their success.

In answering the first research question the study revealed that the majority of Ghanaian women entrepreneurs believed they possessed the following important personal traits: a strong desire for success, “self-confidence, internal locus of control, a desire for independence and responsibility, an openness to innovation, and a high degree of optimism about the success of their entrepreneurial endeavours. The alternative hypothesis was disproved as a result. The findings imply that people's personalities have a big impact on their achievements. There was strong evidence that these Ghanaian women entrepreneurs' personalities and success were highly correlated.

Additionally, these Ghanaian women entrepreneurs were found to have various forms of educational qualifications ranging from primary, secondary/high school to university degree. The traits they possess include the desire to take more risks, control their businesses, determination to improve upon their performance and the desire to take strict decisions for the business. The finding corroborated with Guicui and Xingyuan (2012) who established that women's entrepreneurial success, is influenced by personalities, human capital, femininity, and entrepreneurial motivation. Cabrera and Mauricio (2017) also found that, there are a variety of elements that influence the success of female entrepreneurs at every stage of the entrepreneurial process. These factors can be located and organized at the individual level including the personal characteristics of the entrepreneurs. Determination and resilience were identified by Banda (2018) to contribute to the success of women entrepreneurs which are in accordance with the findings of this study.”

It is revealed in the research that the competency level of women entrepreneurs significantly impact their success. These include the skills to manage the business, the ability to select right management teams, ability “to generate new ideas and the ability to develop new products and services to meet customer demands. Competencies in the areas of staff development and the skill to bond well with teams to drive business success are also critical in the success of the women entrepreneurs. The studies by Raheem (2013) and Schneider (2016) were in agreement with this study. According to Raheem (2013) women are more likely to aspire to entrepreneurial success and believe that they have the capacity, capabilities, and aptitude for female company ownership in countries where society recognizes this. Schneider (2016) also found that functional task-related managerial skills, entrepreneurial characteristic adaptations of self-efficacy, risk-taking and innovation orientations are critical for women's success.”

The findings of the study further revealed that demographic characteristics of entrepreneurial women do not significantly impact the success of their businesses. The age of the women entrepreneurs as well as the educational qualification does not have substantial impact on the success of their businesses. “The marital status and the performance of home duties of the women do not affect the success of the women entrepreneurs. The findings disagreed with the findings of Tlais and Kauser (2019) and Sajilan et al. (2015). Tlais and Kauser (2019) discovered that patriarchal social norms, gender roles, and expectations, as well as societal expectations of women's domestic responsibilities and childbearing roles, all have a part in limiting women's entrepreneurial development and success. Sajilan et al. (2015) also found that the impact of an entrepreneur's demographic features changes depending on the situation. Women entrepreneurs are crucial to a company's development because they possess a unique set of traits like a strong

demand for accomplishment, a high need for knowledge, and an internal locus of control.” They stand out from those who are not self-employed due to these traits.

The study findings show that, external opportunities do not significantly impact the success of women entrepreneurs. These include laws and regulations, coaching from Governmental and non-Governmental Organisations and relieves and tax incentives. This finding disagreed with the findings of Bugawa and Aljuwaisri (2021) and Kalyani and Mounika (2016). Kalyani and Mounika (2016) further indicated that, women's motivations for starting their own businesses go beyond the traditional norms of financial gain, employment independence, personal growth, and well-being. Entrepreneurship is frequently fuelled by a sense of opportunity presented by a shifting environment. Their backgrounds are just as diverse as the reasons for beginning a business; some out of financial necessity, others out of a desire to use their free time in a profitable way, and yet others because they were inspired by a new idea. Bugawa and Aljuwaisri (2021) also found such factors as human capital and external factors such as cultural, economic, legal, administrative to influence the performance of women entrepreneurs.

Regarding the second research question, the research indicated that the availability of resources to women entrepreneurs have significant impact on their success. Access to funding for the business, equipment and qualified labour are important for the success of women businesses. Further access to loans and land for business operations are crucial for the women entrepreneurs. Access to funding for the business, equipment and qualified labour are important for the success of women businesses. Further access to loans and land for business operations are crucial for the women entrepreneurs. The “findings were consistent with the findings of Rani and Hashim (2017) and Sallah and Caesar (2020). Rani and Hashim (2017) mentioned human capital, networking, financial aids, and opportunity as some of the influences. Social capital, human

capital, and reputational capital were all found to be key contributors to the growth of women-owned enterprises by Sallah and Caesar (2020). The study also found that social capital, reputational capital, and human capital all have a favourable and significant impact on women entrepreneurs' success.”

In answering the third research question, The study showed that “the Government of Ghana should create enabling environment for women entrepreneurs to operate and grow their businesses”. This activity should be done through tax waivers, tax holidays, provision of land, fast-tracking businesses registration and improving exchange rates. Personality factors such as the passion to succeed, desire for risk-taking, motivation and control of businesses for women entrepreneurs should be improved through mentorship and coaching. Experienced entrepreneurs in Ghana should coach women entrepreneurs for them to learn important personality factors critical for businesses success. These findings of the research has led to the modification of the original conceptual. Figure 6.1 below shows that personality traits women entrepreneurs, competency of women entrepreneurs and resource availability to women entrepreneurs have positive significant impact on the success of women entrepreneurs in Ghana.

Figure 6.1: Updated Conceptual Framework

Source: author's findings

6.3 Recommendations

The study has established there is a significant impact of the competence of women entrepreneurs on the successes of their entrepreneurial activities. It is therefore recommended that factors “related to the competency of women such as business management skills, problem-solving skills, and decision-making skills should be improved for women entrepreneurs in Ghana. This activity should be done through Governmental and non-governmental organisations with an interest in promoting women entrepreneurs.” Seminars, workshops, and conferences should be organized for the women entrepreneurs by such organisations.

Personality factors such as the passion to succeed, desire for risk-taking, motivation and control of businesses for women entrepreneurs should be improved through mentorship and coaching. Experienced entrepreneurs in Ghana should coach women entrepreneurs in order for them to learn important personality factors critical for businesses success. Businesses cannot flourish with limited resources. Women entrepreneurs in Ghana should be supported with resources such as finance and equipment to grow their businesses. Banks should make loans available for women entrepreneurs at low-interest rates with less cumbersome procedures.

The Government of Ghana should create conducive economic environment to enable Ghanaian women entrepreneurs to operate and grow their businesses. This activity should be done through tax waivers, tax holidays, provision of land, fast-tracking businesses registration and improving exchange rates. The low cost of doing business for women entrepreneurs means that their businesses will be profitable and grow.

6.4 Research Contributions

The purpose of this thesis was to critically explore the factors that play major roles in determining the entrepreneurial success of Ghanaian women. In the subsection that follows, we present a discussion on the contributions made by the current research regarding the purpose of the study and its outcomes.

6.4.1 Contributions

The contributions of the findings of the research may be viewed from the perspectives of the adopted theory, methodological approach employed in conducting the research, and practical contributions to the existing body of knowledge. “The contribution to literature fills the research gap on Ghanaian women entrepreneurs, by highlighting the entrepreneurial success factors

associated with this group of entrepreneurs in the country and how these factors have assisted in helping them to achieve success in their businesses. Women entrepreneurs in Ghana have been the subject of relatively few research. The success determinants of women entrepreneurs from a developing country such as Ghana will add to the existing literature on women entrepreneurship. Furthermore, the contributing information has concentrated on the factors of entrepreneurial success for Ghanaian women entrepreneurs, thereby adding to the existing literature on women entrepreneurship” success.

Practically, the study makes recommendations to women entrepreneurs to explore the contributing factors to the success of their businesses. The research sheds light on how women can use their personality traits and competencies such as skills, experiences, risk-taking, problem-solving skills to develop their businesses. Additionally, the study recommends practical ways of obtaining resources to grow their businesses including investments and loans.

6.5 Recommendations for Further Research

Further studies can look at how “other factors which were not examined in this research influence women entrepreneurs success.” The study could explore factors such as socio-cultural beliefs, mentorship, access to customers, and government support. These factors can be compared to the factors in this research (personality traits, competency, demographic characteristics, external opportunities, and resources) to determine how they influence women entrepreneurs' success.

Further studies can also explore the factors influencing the success of Ghanaian women living abroad. Such a study will take into consideration, the different socio-economic circumstances of foreign countries and how they influence women entrepreneurs' success.

6.6 Limitations of Study

This project started as a Doctor of Philosophy thesis but researcher had to opt for a Master of philosophy due to losing sponsorship for the studies because of the covid pandemic and had to finance his studies from my finances which were very difficult. Data for this study came exclusively from Ghanaian women entrepreneurs as the goal of the study was to recommend to the Ghanaian women entrepreneurs ways by which they can improve the success of their businesses. This placed limits on involving all other Ghanaian women entrepreneurs living abroad. Therefore, this research was unable to reflect the factors influencing women entrepreneurs' success abroad.

Another drawback of this study is that it only used a quantitative research method, which was done to gain fresh viewpoints and/or build on existing ones on entrepreneurial success determinants. Qualitative data collection methods, which allow for deeper exploration of ideas, were not employed in this study, thereby placing some limitations on the outcome of the study. The researcher employed a cross-sectional analysis for the purposes of exploratory analysis on the factors that contribute to entrepreneurial success of Ghanaian women. However, a longitudinal study could prove more adequate in offering an explanation about the factors that determine the success of Ghanaian women entrepreneurs in their businesses.

Finally, the study was limited to Ghanaian women entrepreneurs in Greater Accra Region and Ashanti Region. This is a limitation of the study as women entrepreneurs in the remaining fourteen regions in Ghana were excluded from the study. The situation limits the ability to generalise the research findings.

6.7 Conclusions

The research draws the following conclusions from the study. Women business owners contribute substantially towards the growth and expansion of the commercial sector of Ghana. Their success and contributions to economy of Ghana are influenced by factors related to their selves as well as external economic factors. On a personal level, women entrepreneurs' personality qualities have a stronger impact on their success. Strong-willed Ghanaian women are able to use their personality influence to advance their enterprises. “The will to succeed, the ability to make crucial business decisions, and the willingness to take measured risks are crucial variables affecting the business success of women entrepreneurs.”

Further, the experiences of female entrepreneurs in managing their firms cannot be disregarded as a factor in determining their success. Women are able to use their prior work experience to boost their new businesses. They learn from their failures in previous economic ventures to successfully operate their current businesses. This study concluded that the fact that a person being a woman does not affect the success of their company. Similarly, the age, education, and family history of female entrepreneurs had no larger impact on their success. On an external level, the availability of resources, especially sources of financing, has a stronger effect on the success of entrepreneurial women. Inadequate financing prevents the women from expanding and also “investing in the day-to-day activities of their businesses.” Women entrepreneurs in Ghana face difficulties in raising debt financing from Banks and other external sources. The result is their inability to expand and sometimes the failure of their ventures. It is important for women with the drive to succeed in their businesses to leverage their personal qualities and experiences to effectively manage their businesses whiles exploring external funding sources to grow.

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Appendix 1

UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND

QUESTIONNAIRE FOR RESPONDENTS

Dear Respondent,

My name is Francis Mensah, I am a Master of philosophy student from the University of the West of Scotland in the United Kingdom. As part of my studies, I am working on research project on “*Female Entrepreneurship in Ghana: Factors of Entrepreneurial Success towards Women Entrepreneurs*”. The researcher seeks your participation in this study, which is a partial requirement for the award of Master of philosophy Certificate. Data collected is solely meant for academic purposes and for this research only. The privacy and confidentiality of the data you give will strictly be upheld. You have the freedom to participate or opt out of the study at any point without suffering any consequences. Kindly answer the questions below as honest as possible.

SECTION A: SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION OF RESPONDENT

1. What is your age?

- (i) 20 – 30 years [] (ii) 31-40 years [] (iii) 41-50 years []
(iv) 51-60 years [] (v) Above 60 years []

2. What is your highest level of education?

- (i) High School and below []
- (ii) Diploma []
- (iii) First Degree []
- (iv) Masters' Degree []
- (v) Doctorate Degree []
- (iv) No Formal Education []

3. Number of years in business

- (i) Below 1 year []
- (ii) 1 - 5 years []
- (iii) 6 - 10 years []
- (iv) Above 10 years []

4. Work Status of Entrepreneur

- (i) Full time []
- (ii) Part time []

5. Number of Employees

- (i) less than 10 employees []
- (ii) 10 – 20 employees []
- (iii) 21 – 50 employees []
- (iv) Above 50 employees []

6. Average annual income

- (i) less than \$10, 000 []
- (ii) \$ 10, 000 – \$50, 000 []
- (iii) \$ 51, 000 – \$100, 000 []
- (iv) Above \$ 100,000 []

SECTION B: INTERNAL FACTORS INFLUENCING ENTREPRENEURIAL SUCCESS

Please tick Strongly Disagree (1), Disagree (2), Uncertain (3), Agree (4) and Strongly Agree (5) to indicate the extent of agreement with the factors measuring personality, competence and demographics.

Personality	(SA)	(A)	(U)	(D)	(SD)
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	5	4	3	2	1
1. I have desire to take more risks					
2. My business can be generally classified as riskier					
3. I have the drive to take control of my business activities.					
4. I get to make decisions for the business as I prefer					
5. I am motivated to achieve more by improving on my past performance					

Competence	(SA) 5	(A) 4	(U) 3	(D) 2	(SD) 1
1. I have the skills to manage the business					
2. I get the opportunity to select my management team					
3. I brainstorm to bring new ideas for the business					
4. New products and services are continuously developed					
5. I bond well with staff to achieve business goals					
6. We train staff on interpersonal skills for team work					

Demographics	(SA) 5	(A) 4	(U) 3	(D) 2	(SD) 1
1. I receive support from family and friends					
2. My experience in business helps me to succeed					
3. My educational qualification enhances my business decisions					
4. My business partners do not discriminate against me because I am a woman					
5. Performance of home duties do not affect my business					

SECTION C: EXTERNAL FACTORS INFLUENCING ENTREPRENEURIAL SUCCESS

Please tick Strongly Disagree (1), Disagree (2), Uncertain (3), Agree (4) and Strongly Agree (5) to indicate the extent of agreement with the opportunity and resource variables as they related to external factors influencing entrepreneurship.

Opportunity	(SA) 5	(A) 4	(U) 3	(D) 2	(SD) 1
1. Competition is limited in my line of business					
2. The business laws and regulations favour female entrepreneurship					
3. Women entrepreneurs have the same business opportunities as men					
4. Women entrepreneurs receive coaching from Governmental and non-Governmental Organisations					
5. There are tax incentives for women entrepreneurs					

Resource	(SA) 5	(A) 4	(U) 3	(D) 2	(SD) 1
1. Obtaining different funding for the business is not difficult					
2. There are qualified labour to work with					
3. Banks procedures to obtain business loans are not cumbersome					
4. The cost of assets for the business operations are moderate					
5. Interest on business loans are moderate					
6. I do not find it tiresome to find a location for the business					

SECTION C: MEASUREMENT OF WOMEN ENTREPRENEURIAL SUCCESS

Please tick Strongly Disagree (1), Disagree (2), Uncertain (3), Agree (4) and Strongly Agree (5) to indicate the extent of agreement with entrepreneurial success indicators below.

Entrepreneurial Success	(SA)	(A)	(U)	(D)	(SD)
	5	4	3	2	1
1. I have experienced increase in sales in the last three years					
2. I am able to reinvest more than 50% of the business profit generated					
3. The business is able to cover cost and make profit continuously					
4. The business is able to develop new products and services					
5. I am confident that, my business will survive into the future					
6. I am able to continuously employ new staff and create employment					
7. The business is able to offer high quality products and services					
8. I see constant growth in my business activities					
9. I have employees with the right skills to make the business succeed.					

END. THANKS FOR PARTICIPATING

Appendix 2 Participant Consent Form

Participant consent form

Please answer the following question by circling the response that applies

1. I have read the participant information sheet for this study and have details explained

Yes / no

2. My questions about the study have been answered to my satisfaction and I understand that I may ask further questions at any point

Yes / No

3. I understand that I am free to withdraw from the study within the time limit outlined in the information sheet, without giving a reason for my withdrawal or decline to answer a particular question in the study without any consequences to my future treatment by the researcher

Yes / No

4. I agree to provide information to the researcher under conditions of confidentiality set out in the information sheet

Yes / No

5. I wish to participate in the study under the conditions set out in the information sheet

Yes /No

6. I consent to the information collected for the purpose of this research study, once anonymized to be used for any other purposes

Yes / No

Participant's name.....

Participant's signature.....
date.....

Contact details.....

Researcher's name.....

Researcher's signature.....
date.....

Researcher's contact details:

(name, address, contact number of researcher)

Participant Information Sheet

1. Research Project Title

Female Entrepreneurship in Ghana: Factors of Entrepreneurial Success towards Women Entrepreneurs

2. Invitation

You are being invited to take part in this research project. Before you decide to do so, it is important you understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish.

Ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part. Thank you for reading this.

3. What is the project's purpose?

This research project aims to investigate how success factors affect the business of Ghanaian female entrepreneurs.

4. Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen because as a female entrepreneur in Ghana you will have knowledge about factors that affect the success of your business

5. Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part you will be able to keep a copy of this information sheet and you should indicate your agreement to the online consent form. You can still withdraw at any time. You do not have to give a reason.

6. What will happen to me if I take part?

You will be asked to complete a questionnaire which we estimate will take you 15 to 30

minutes.

7. What do I have to do?

Please answer the questions in the questionnaire. There are no other commitments or lifestyle restrictions associated with participating.

8. What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

Participating in the research is not anticipated to cause you any disadvantages or discomfort.

The potential physical and/or psychological harm or distress will be the same as any experienced in everyday life

9. What are the possible benefits of taking part?

There are no immediate benefits for those people participating in the project,

10. What happens if the research study stops earlier than expected?

Should the research stop earlier than planned and you are affected in any way we will tell you and explain why.

11. What if something goes wrong?

If you have any complaints about the project in the first instance you can contact me or my supervisors. If you feel your complaint has not been handled to your satisfaction you can contact my supervisors to take your complaint further (see below).

12. Will my taking part in this project be kept confidential?

All the information that I collect about you during the course of the research will be kept strictly confidential. You will not be able to be identified or identifiable in any reports or publications. Your company will also not be identified or identifiable.

13. Will I be recorded, and how will the recorded media be used?

You will not be recorded in any way other than your input to the questionnaire without separate permission being gained from you.

14. What type of information will be sought from me and why is the collection of this information relevant for achieving the research project's objectives?

The questionnaire will ask you about your opinions on how you run your company.

Your views and experience are just what the project is interested in exploring.

15. What will happen to the results of the research project?

The results of the study will be summarised in my final dissertation as part of the requirements for an Mphil degree. They may also be published in peer-reviewed scientific journals, and presented at conferences.

16. Who is organising and funding the research?

This research is being organized and funded by me as part of my Mphil programme

17. Who has ethically reviewed the project?

This project has been ethically approved by School of business and creative industries(UWS) ethics committee

18. Contacts for further information

Dr Dina Nziku- [REDACTED]) –Director of studies

Prof. John Struthers- [REDACTED]) 2nd supervisor

Personal details withheld.

APPENDIX 4

21/12/2021

Dear Francis Mensah,

Your application 17451: Factors of entrepreneurial success of Ghanaian women, submission 14717, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC .

You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr John Quin

